

**THIRD CONSULTATION ON THE
USE OF BIG DATA IN LATIN
AMERICA AND THE CARIBBEAN
2024**

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1. Executive summary

This report pertains to the third edition of the International Consultation on the Use of Big Data in Latin America and the Caribbean, conducted annually by the UN Regional Hub for Big Data in Brazil. It was undertaken in the context of the Statistical and Geoscientific Production Modernization Project, coordinated by the Brazilian Institute of Geography and Statistics (IBGE) and the United Nations Population Fund (UNFPA). The document synthesizes advances, challenges, and perspectives on using big data in producing official and experimental statistics in Latin American and Caribbean countries.

The study encompassed a literature review, surveys, and in-depth interviews conducted in 2024, building upon consultations undertaken in 2022 and 2023. The goal was to evaluate the capabilities of national statistical institutes (NSIs) and offer recommendations on utilizing big data for statistical production.

Two instruments were employed: online questionnaires and in-depth interviews with representatives from 24 countries in the region that had participated in previous consultations. In 2024, 15 responses to the online questionnaire were received, and 12 in-depth interviews were conducted with countries that accepted the invitation to participate. The topics related to big data were categorized into four dimensions: the production of official statistics, experimental statistics, studies on the use of big data, and plans for its application. Additionally, the interviews explored using big data for other purposes, required resources for working with big data, and expertise to share.

The online questionnaire and in-depth interviews addressed overlapping themes and questions, and the procedure was first starting with the questionnaire and then facilitating the subsequent deepening of responses through interviews. The research necessitated the standardization of certain concepts, such as big data, which the United Nations Economic Commission for Europe defines as data produced in large volume, velocity, and variety, distinguishing it from survey data or administrative records.

The online questionnaire received responses from 15 countries, 12 of which also participated in the in-depth interviews. The results identified eight countries utilizing big data for official statistics, ten for experimental statistics, twelve conducting studies, and thirteen with plans. An increase in the number of countries engaged with big data was noted, particularly in the transition from experimental statistics to official use and future planning. Regarding big data types, satellite imagery, and web scraping were frequently cited due to their accessibility and cost-efficiency. These types were consistently mentioned across official

statistics, experimental statistics, and studies supplemented by mobile data in planning contexts. In terms of topics, population statistics were most commonly addressed.

The in-depth interviews, conducted over two months with technicians from 12 countries, revealed varying objectives and experiences involving web scraping and satellite imagery, the most common types of big data. Mobile data, although of interest to several countries, was scarcely mentioned.

Challenges and resources necessary for working with big data were detailed, highlighting the importance of inter-country collaboration, experience sharing, and access to training resources. Key barriers identified included inadequate technological infrastructure and a lack of trained personnel. Legal issues concerning data access and ethical concerns regarding private data usage were also noted.

Big data offers transformative opportunities for statistical production in Latin America and the Caribbean but requires coordinated efforts in capacity building, infrastructure development, and governance. Experience sharing and support from international organizations such as the UN Regional Hub for Big Data in Brazil and the Economic Commission for Latin America and the Caribbean (ECLAC) were cited as essential resources for overcoming barriers and ensuring these technologies' effective and ethical use.

The report's recommendations address challenges associated with big data across legal, ethical, technical, technological, operational, and methodological dimensions. These recommendations propose various possibilities without prescribing a single path or definitive solutions, allowing each country to identify its unique priorities and strengthen its big data capabilities accordingly.

This report pertains to the third edition of the International Consultation on the Use of Big Data in Latin America and the Caribbean, conducted annually by the UN Regional Hub for Big Data in Brazil. It was executed within the Statistical and Geoscientific Production Modernization Project framework, coordinated by the Brazilian Institute of Geography and Statistics (IBGE) and the United Nations Population Fund (UNFPA). The document synthesizes progress, challenges, and perspectives concerning the use of big data in producing official and experimental statistics across the region.

This project encompasses two primary workstreams, one of which, “Modernization of statistical and geoscientific production processes to enhance the quality of information through partnerships, integration of new data sources and administrative records, and adoption of advanced production techniques,” frames the scope of this report. Specifically, activity 2.3.1

focuses on “Enhancing and systematizing the collection, processing, storage, and integration of administrative records, databases, and unstructured data.”

Under the Terms of Reference 2.1.1 for consultancy in qualitative research, in-depth interviews, and data analysis, the consultancy's context, scope, and deliverables are outlined. The scope involves expanding global experiences in utilizing big data for statistics, providing comprehensive regional insights, and identifying best practices and gaps.

The consultancy entails conducting an in-depth study on using big data by national statistical institutes in Latin America and the Caribbean for statistical production. This includes conducting interviews, analyzing data, and producing a final document comprising three interconnected deliverables.

The first deliverable is a report summarizing interviews with countries participating in at least one of the 2022, 2023, and 2024 consultations.

The second is an analysis of the collected data.

The third and final deliverable incorporates a literature review and 2024 consultation results, assessing NSIs' capacities to leverage big data for statistical production.

The project commenced on June 6, 2024, with a seven-month timeline. Deliverables were organized 60, 120, and 180 days after the contract initiation.

This report provides an in-depth analysis of information collected on big data usage in Latin American and Caribbean countries through the 2024 consultation—the consultation employed two data collection tools: online questionnaires and in-depth interviews.

The activities and findings align with the UN Regional Hub for Big Data's work program (September 2023 - August 2024), aiming to strengthen cooperation among regional producers of official statistics and advance big data applications for statistical innovation.

2. Introduction

This report pertains to the third edition of the International Consultation on the Use of Big Data in Latin America and the Caribbean, conducted annually by the UN Regional Hub for Big Data in Brazil. It was carried out within the Statistical and Geoscientific Production Modernization Project framework, coordinated by the Brazilian Institute of Geography and Statistics (IBGE) and the United Nations Population Fund (UNFPA). The document synthesizes advances, challenges, and perspectives concerning the use of big data in producing official and experimental statistics in Latin American and Caribbean countries.

This project comprises two main workstreams, one of which frames the scope of this report: "Modernization of statistical and geoscientific production processes to enhance the quality of information through partnerships, incorporation of new competencies, integration with new databases and administrative records, adoption of innovative production techniques, and improvement of systems and processes guided by generic models for statistical and geoscientific production." Regarding this workstream, the scope can be identified under activity 2.3.1: "Enhancement and systematization of the collection, prospecting, reception, storage, processing, integration, and use of administrative records, databases, and unstructured data."

Through Terms of Reference 2.1.1 for consultancy in qualitative research, in-depth interviews, and data analysis, the context and objectives of the consultancy and the scope of work and deliverables are outlined. In terms of context and scope, the work is related to expanding global experiences in utilizing big data for statistics, providing detailed information on "adopted practices and emerging opportunities in the use of big data"¹ through a report that presents a comprehensive and detailed regional scenario, enabling the identification of best practices and potential gaps.

From the scope of work perspective, the consultant is expected to "conduct an in-depth study on the use of big data for the production of statistics by the national statistical institutes of Latin America and the Caribbean."² The activities involve conducting in-depth interviews, data analysis, and document preparation, culminating in three interrelated deliverables. These deliverables are connected so that the third and final product incorporates the contents of the first and second while including additional elements not present in the earlier ones.

¹ United Nations Population Fund (UNFPA). Termo de referência 2.1.1 – consultoria em pesquisa qualitativa, entrevistas em profundidade e análise de dados.

² Idem.

The first deliverable consists of a report summarizing in-depth interviews with countries that participated in at least one of the Consultations held in 2022, 2023, and 2024. The second deliverable involves an analysis of the collected data, and the third is a final document that includes a literature review and the results of the 2024 Consultation, assessing the capacity of national statistical institutes to utilize big data for statistical production.

The work commenced on June 6, 2024, and was expected to last seven months. The deliverables were temporally organized from the contract's start, with deadlines set at 60, 120, and 180 days. The consultancy formally began upon the consultant's signature of the contract.

This report provides an in-depth and detailed analysis of the information gathered on using big data in Latin American and Caribbean countries through the 2024 International Consultation on the Use of Big Data in Latin America and the Caribbean, conducted by the UN Regional Hub for Big Data in Brazil. Aiming to capture each country's specific reality, the 2024 Consultation employed two data collection instruments: online questionnaires and in-depth interviews.

It is also worth noting that this report and the activities undertaken for its preparation are included in the work program for September 2023 to August 2024 of the UN Regional Hub for Big Data in Brazil, within its first planning line, to strengthen connections and promote cooperation among producers of official statistics in the region. Precisely, this aligns with its detailed activity 1.2, "Use of Big Data in Latin America and the Caribbean – 3rd Consultation,"³ as well as the broader objective of "advancing the use of big data to enhance the production of official statistics, fostering knowledge sharing and the development of innovative initiatives in Latin America and the Caribbean."

2.1. Report structure

Regarding the content presented, the report is structured as follows:

- 3. Use of big data around the world
- 4. Results of the 2024 survey
- 5. Results of the in-depth interviews
- 6. Findings
- 7. Recommendations

³ https://hub.ibge.gov.br/programme_port_2023_2024.htm. Access in October 2024.

In the section Use of Big Data Around the World, experiences and their relationship with those mapped in Latin America and the Caribbean are presented, focusing on using big data and the production of statistics.

The subsequent section, Results of the 2024 Survey, provides summaries of the data collected, analyses, and comparisons with the surveys conducted in 2022 and 2023, following the same order in which the questions appear in the survey questionnaire.

In Results of the In-Depth Interviews, testimonies illustrate the experiences collected for each question in the interview script, which closely resembles the questionnaire used in the 2024 survey.

The final two sections, Findings and Recommendations, address observations on the results derived from the interviews and their comparison with the survey, as well as suggestions for addressing challenges across different dimensions, including legal, ethical, technical, technological, operational, and methodological aspects.

The text first outlines the specific structures of each instrument, survey, and in-depth interview before presenting the results. The topics covered in both instruments are similar, but the application methods differ significantly.

2.2. Concepts used

It is essential to highlight that, given the focus on big data, the definition presented by McFeely (2019), commonly referred to as the "three Vs," was adopted. This definition describes big data as information or data characterized by high volume, high velocity, and high variety.⁴

In the exact text, McFeely, citing the definition of the United Nations Statistical Commission and its similarity to the previous definition, emphasized: “data sources that can be described as having large volume, high velocity, and variety, requiring economically viable and innovative processing methods for enhanced insights and decision-making.” (McFeely, 2019, p.122).

McFeely's two definitions are consistent and complementary, emphasizing that big data sources, in addition to being defined by the three Vs, require innovative and economically viable processing methods.

⁴ Definition from European Commission from 2014: <https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/node/69/printable/pdf>. Access in October 2024.

This report's observations and findings align with this definition, ensuring no impact on the survey responses, which were primarily closed-ended. It is worth clarifying that a closed-ended survey offers only objective responses, such as “yes” or “no.”

On the other hand, it becomes evident that in-depth interviews had a greater impact, as the testimonies collected did not always adhere to the mentioned concept of big data.

2.3. Context and methodology

The relevance of analyzing information from the 2024 Consultation is underscored by its contextual linkage with two previous consultations conducted in 2022 and 2023. These efforts highlight the importance of continuous research that provides a comprehensive and evolving perspective on countries through data analysis.

Through diverse research tools, the consultation enabled the detailed exploration of "the types of big data, the methods employed, and the topics studied" (United Nations, 2024, p.1). A shared objective across all editions was to track advances in the use of big data by national statistical institutes (NSIs) in Latin American and Caribbean countries. The research activities were carried out under the auspices of the UN Regional Hub for Big Data, based in Brazil, with support from the United Nations Population Fund (UNFPA).

The consultations relied on two main types of instruments: online questionnaires and in-depth interviews.

In the years preceding 2024, the consultations exclusively employed online questionnaires. In 2024, the online questionnaire was made available initially, followed by invitations to in-depth interviews. Invitations were sent to all 24 countries that had responded to the online questionnaire during any of the three years of consultations.

In all consultations, the questionnaires were available in three languages—Portuguese, Spanish, and English—and completed voluntarily by representatives of the respective national statistical institutes.

Responses to the online questionnaires could be submitted by more than one individual, allowing a single country to provide multiple responses from different informants.

When multiple responses were submitted for a single country, the data were consolidated to retain all completed information, minimizing the risk of losing potentially significant data.

The in-depth interviews were conducted following email invitations from the UN Regional Hub for Big Data coordination team in Latin America and the Caribbean. Upon receiving responses, further actions were taken. Not all responses indicated a willingness to participate in the interviews, but when acceptance was received, interview scheduling ensued.

After receiving an email confirming participation availability, additional communications were exchanged to finalize the interview date, share information about the topics to be discussed, and provide the contact with the most recent online questionnaire response. This last step was intended to aid participants in recalling the information previously shared by their country on the topic.

A detailed script outlined the structure of the in-depth interviews. This script was followed rigorously during all interviews, ensuring consistency. The script mirrored the logic of the online questionnaire, with initial questions focused on the use of big data and concluding questions addressing motivations, needs, and other related topics.

The in-depth interviews were conducted by pairs of researchers using the native language of the interviewed country's team. All interviews were recorded for subsequent analysis, information extraction, and clarification when necessary.

3. Use of big data around the world

The adoption of big data worldwide is driven by its potential to transform the production of official statistics, particularly in monitoring the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) (Halderen et al., 2021). A 2015 United Nations Global Working Group study found that only 2% of countries utilized big data for SDG monitoring, while 30% used it for price statistics.

Many countries have explored non-traditional data sources to track specific SDG targets, including poverty indicators and environmental conditions. In Asia, for instance, China has advanced pilot projects integrating geospatial data to monitor 12 SDG indicators, providing real-time insights into local socioeconomic and environmental conditions. Additionally, the Philippines has promoted collaboration among various institutions to identify over 80 SDG indicators. South Korea has progressed in using big data from satellite images, georeferenced data, and mobility data, among others (Halderen et al., 2021). However, Halderen notes a lack of examples involving mobile phone data, scanner data, or social media.

Numerous big data applications in statistical production have been documented in Europe and the United States (Abdulkadri, 2016), often as alternatives or complements to traditional data sources. Examples include mobility, health, and price statistics, with 21 studies

on big data applications listed. Not all experiences with big data are documented in articles, suggesting the number of implementations may be higher.

In Latin America and the Caribbean (LAC), the use of big data has grown as an alternative to traditional methods, especially in response to financial and structural limitations exacerbated by the COVID-19 pandemic (Silva et al., 2023). Countries such as Brazil, Chile, Colombia, and Mexico have implemented experimental projects using big data sources, such as satellite imagery and social media data, to produce statistics on prices and well-being (Silva, 2023). This context differs from more developed nations, where big data is established as a complementary resource, while in LAC, it emerges as a potential solution to address the lack of resources and limited infrastructure in national statistical institutes (NSIs) (Silva et al., 2023).

The integration of sensor data and satellite imagery stands out in LAC. For example, Honduras has used such data to map poverty and malnutrition, illustrating the potential of big data for real-time monitoring of critical development issues (Silva et al., 2023). In Colombia, the National Administrative Department of Statistics (DANE) employs satellite images to generate indicators on land use and coverage, aiding the formulation of policies for sustainable development and environmental conservation (Silva, 2023). These advancements demonstrate how big data can fill critical gaps hindering public policy development.

Challenges remain for the full adoption of big data in LAC, including the need for technical capacity and adequate resources. The lack of IT infrastructure and skilled professionals makes big data complex (Silva et al., 2023). Legal and ethical issues related to data privacy and usage also pose challenges, especially in developing countries. Data governance, including the safe and responsible use of social media and mobile data, is a common concern across LAC countries (Silva, 2023). While big data initiatives offer promising solutions, the lack of clear regulations and limited personal data protection undermine public trust in these initiatives (Silva et al., 2023).

ECLAC and the UN Regional Hub for Big Data in Brazil have played a crucial role in supporting the adoption of big data in LAC. These organizations facilitate consultations and studies to identify best practices and promote capacity-building for NSOs⁵ (Silva, 2023). Through training and technology sharing, these initiatives aim to reduce disparities in big data access and usage among countries in the region, fostering more balanced and sustainable

⁵ National Statistical Offices.

adoption (Silva et al., 2023). This support is vital for LAC countries to develop data autonomy and reduce their reliance on financial resources for research and data production.

The use of big data for SDG monitoring exemplifies its practical applications. In various regions, big data sources, such as satellite imagery and social media, are used to rapidly map environmental and social changes, which is particularly useful during the pandemic (Halderen et al., 2021). However, access to and reliability of big data raise concerns about the quality and representativeness of results, especially in countries with technological limitations. According to Silva (2023), the lack of standardization in data obtained through methods like web scraping and social media challenges the production of reliable statistics.

Although big data offers innovative and potentially transformative solutions for statistical production in LAC, effective implementation depends on continued investments in infrastructure, capacity building, and governance. Even in countries like Brazil, Chile, Colombia, and Mexico, which have made regional advancements, there is still significant progress before big data becomes a familiar and reliable practice for official statistics (Silva, 2023; Silva et al., 2023). Experience sharing with more advanced nations and ongoing support from international organizations will be essential for Latin American NSIs to achieve global standards in big data usage.

Cooperation among countries and the development of regional partnerships are seen as ways to overcome limitations and promote the ethical and safe use of big data. In LAC, similar efforts could help mitigate infrastructure challenges and improve data representativeness while promoting transparency and public engagement (Silva et al., 2023).

Globally, big data has become a critical tool for monitoring indicators and informing decision-making, particularly in the context of the SDGs. From a global perspective, Halderen (2021) highlights advancements in Europe and the United States, mainly using non-traditional data, such as land observations and geospatial information, to monitor various SDG indicators. Similarly, Abdulkadri (2016) emphasizes the potential of big data for these purposes. These data sources offer alternatives to fill gaps in traditional data, providing information at lower costs.

In the specific context of LAC, progress in big data usage continues to face significant challenges but shows growing potential. According to Silva (2023), the NSIs of countries like Brazil, Colombia, and Mexico already use big data sources to produce official and experimental statistics. Applications include satellite imagery to map poverty and malnutrition, as in Honduras, and web scraping for price collection in Brazil. These examples demonstrate the

NSIs' adaptation to new technologies and ability to respond to statistical production needs more efficiently and comprehensively, even amidst financial and structural constraints.

However, the use of big data in LAC faces structural and socioeconomic obstacles that hinder widespread implementation. Silva (2023) notes that issues such as the lack of technological infrastructure and financial resources impair the development of these initiatives. Moreover, data governance and privacy remain critical concerns for NSIs, as many countries still lack robust legislation to address data ownership and anonymization. These challenges highlight the need for regional policies and strategies that promote collaboration among countries to strengthen big data collection and analysis capabilities for statistical purposes.

The support of international organizations, such as ECLAC, has been crucial in fostering the use of big data in the region. In partnership with the UN Regional Hub for Big Data in Brazil, ECLAC has conducted consultations and studies to map big data usage among NSIs, identifying priority areas for capacity building and infrastructure development. International cooperation helps bridge knowledge and resource gaps, facilitating the use of new technologies for statistical production and sharing best practices.

Big data usage for statistical production in LAC is solidifying, albeit with challenges and opportunities reflective of regional dynamics. The ability to extract meaningful data from sources like social media, satellite imagery, and sensor devices offers a promising perspective for statistical production. Overcoming institutional barriers and implementing robust legislation is essential for big data to contribute effectively to SDG monitoring.

4. Results of the 2024 Survey

The survey was conducted using an online questionnaire implemented through Google Forms, featuring text in the three main languages of the region: Spanish, English, and Portuguese (Appendix A). The questionnaire comprised structuring questions related to using big data for producing official and experimental statistics, studies, and plans for using big data in statistical production. Additionally, it addressed the resources required for utilizing big data and experiences to be shared with other institutes.

4.1. Structure of the questionnaire

The online questionnaires used in the surveys were structured into two parts each year. The first part consisted of four closed-ended structuring questions. In 2024, the second part included four open-ended final questions about experiences, suggestions, needs, etc.

The four structuring questions were as follows:

- Does the Statistical Institute use big data for official statistics?
- Does the Statistical Institute use big data for experimental statistics?
- Does the Statistical Institute study the use of big data for statistics?
- Does the Statistical Institute plan to initiate new uses of big data?

The order of these questions suggests a scale, implying a cumulative process through which official statistics could be produced using big data, beginning with planning for future big data use.

However, it is essential to note that there is no single or unequivocal path from planning to producing official statistics using big data. Even when considering that institutional and structural development may be important factors for this purpose, countries may adopt diverse approaches. For instance, conducting studies and experimental statistics may be part of the pathway for some nations.

Thus, the questions do not establish a mandatory sequence for big data work. From an institutional perspective, producing information requires planning to mobilize resources. Based on such planning, further steps may involve production, structuring, and identifying responsible actors. Subsequently, inputs, tasks, and workflows must be developed for implementation. The implementation itself may require internal validation testing before public-facing production.

The table below presents the list of types or sources of big data for each year.

Table 1 – Types of big data by Consultation

Consultation Year		
2022	2023	2024
Credit card transactions	Financial transactions	Financial transactions
Criminal records	-	-
Health records	Health records	Health indicators
Mobile phone/ CDR	Mobile phone	Mobile phone
Road sensors	Road sensors	Road sensors
Satellite imagery	Satellite imagery	Satellite imagery
Scanner data	Scanner data	Scanner data
Ship identification (AIS)	Ship identification	Ship identification
Smart meter	Smart meter	Smart meter
Social media	Social media	-
Web scraping	Web scraping	Web scraping

Source: United Nations Regional Hub for Big Data in Brazil. Internacional Consultation on the use of Big Data in Latin America and the Caribbean, 2022, 2023 and 2024.

A quick analysis shows a significant standardization of options across the three surveys. In 2022 and 2023, there were ten categories of big data types, eight identical, while the remaining two were expressed in analogous terms.

In reviewing the column corresponding to the 2024 survey, it is clear that there were nine types of big data, with four identical to those from 2022 and 2023 and the remaining five compatible with expressions that already existed in 2023.

It is essential to assess the relevance of these differences. For example, the variation sometimes lies solely in the terminology used, as seen with "Web Collection" or "Web Scraping." Such divergences are related to the common usage of the concept in a specific language. For instance, while the term may have evolved with different wording in Portuguese, observations in another country indicate that a term may have remained unchanged over the years.

On the other hand, it is essential to emphasize the consistency of certain big data types examined. The difference between the three years is noticeable in the absence of the "Social Media" concept in 2024, while the concept of "Web Collection" was modified to "Web Scraping," a broader term encompassing various ways of measuring big data.

Regarding the topics, the table below presents the options used.

Table 2 – Topics of big data by Consultation

Consultation Year		
2022	2023	2024
Agriculture / land use	Agriculture	Agriculture
Crime and corruption	-	-
Disaster risk reduction	Disaster risk reduction	-
Energy / environment	-	Environment
Geographic / spatial	-	-
Health / disease	Health	-
Labor market	Labor market	-
Population / migration	Population	Population
Poverty / inequality	Poverty and inequality	-
Prices	Prices	Prices
Transport / urban mobility	Urban Mobility	-
Turismo	-	-

Source: United Nations Regional Hub for Big Data in Brazil. Internacional Consultation on the use of Big Data in Latin America and the Caribbean, 2022, 2023 and 2024.

The table highlights a reduction in response options over the years: in 2022, there were 12 options, whereas in 2024, only four options remained. Of the four options in 2024, 3 are identical to those in 2023: "Prices," "Population," and "Agriculture." Although not exact, the fourth option, "Environment," is closely related to terms used in previous years. It is broader, encompassing responses such as "Disaster Risk Reduction" from 2023 and 2022.

Data analysis demonstrates an apparent reduction in response options for using big data over the years, with no new categories created. While this reduction limits the richness of the collected information, it simplifies the questionnaire and reflects a trend toward strengthening the use of big data in specific areas.

The four structuring questions include previously detailed options for "Types" and "Topics," followed by an open-ended field for respondents to indicate other combinations of "Type" and "Topic."

The 2024 consultation questionnaire was designed to allow simultaneous identification of big data "Types" and "Topics" within a matrix format, where "Types" were listed in columns and "Topics" in rows.

Notably, this simultaneous indication was unavailable in the 2022 and 2023 questionnaires. In those surveys, respondents could specify the type of big data used or identify the topic in which it was applied, but not simultaneously.

At the end of the questionnaires for all three consultations, general questions covered similar themes, such as limitations and needs for using big data or expertise that could be shared with other countries.

In 2024, four open-ended final questions were included, as follows:

- Does the Statistical Institute have any resources or expertise in using big data that can be shared with other countries? If so, what are they?
- What are the limitations and needs of using big data in statistical production in your country?
- Indicate the training topics of most significant interest or immediate need.
- Do you have any additional suggestions that could help the Hub plan actions to support the use of big data in the region?

From the perspective of the structuring questions, a significant difference is evident in the 2024 consultation with the introduction of the matrix-based indication of "Types of big data" and "Topics," enabling their simultaneous selection.

Regarding the four open-ended final questions, the 2024 questionnaire introduced significant changes by expanding the final questions from previous years. These now include new possibilities, such as sharing experiences, identifying needs for working with big data, pinpointing training topics, and suggesting actions for the Hub to support using big data in the region.

4.2. Survey participation

Participation in the 2024 survey was lower than in previous years. The table below provides this information, organized by year, the number of participating countries, and the total number of responses received annually. It is important to note that in all years, a country's participation or adherence to the consultation occurred through responses provided by one or more professionals from the respective national statistical institute.

Regarding the 2024 Consultation, 15 countries responded to the questionnaire, 12 were submitted between February and June of the same year, and three were interviewed in July during the in-depth interview period.

Countries with multiple responses—where more than one individual completed the questionnaire—include Brazil, Cuba, Panama, Peru, and Uruguay in 2022, and Bolivia, Brazil, Mexico, and Peru in 2023. As expected, in 2024, the same phenomenon occurred in some

countries—Brazil, Cuba, and Peru—totaling only three countries. In 2022, there were five countries with more than one respondent, while in 2023, there were four. Notably, only Brazil and Peru had multiple respondents across all three years, which may indicate greater institutional attention to the topic.

In 2024, 15 countries participated. It is worth mentioning that three (Bonaire, Colombia, and Uruguay) did not participate spontaneously. Their responses were developed during in-depth interviews, consisting of virtual meetings held from July 2024 with professionals from their national statistical institutes. Consequently, the three responses collected by the interview team displayed slightly different characteristics compared to spontaneous responses, as they adhered rigorously to the concepts used in the survey, unlike responses where participants relied on their interpretations of the questions.

Regarding participation by geographic area, Silva et al. (2023) observed increased involvement in Caribbean countries between 2022 and 2023 but decreased participation in South American countries. In 2024, spontaneous participation was the lowest across the three years, with only 12 responses, including just two from Caribbean countries.

It should also be noted that some countries participated in the survey to indicate that they do not work with big data. This was the case for Grenada and Guatemala. Thus, responding to the consultation or participating in the survey does not necessarily reflect a country's investment or involvement with the topic of big data.

The table below highlights these differences. It lists all countries that responded to the consultations at any time, their responses in each survey year, and their participation in in-depth interviews. For each year, codes indicate the country's responses to the four structuring questions in the survey.

Of the 24 countries that participated in at least one consultation, ten participated in all three years, another ten participated in only one, and four participated in two consultations.

Notably, 12 of the 15 countries that participated in the 2024 Consultation also participated in in-depth interviews, which required greater time availability and commitment to the topic. The table below summarizes responses from the 2022, 2023, and 2024 consultations, noting that the 2024 consultation included both a survey and in-depth interviews. In contrast, the previous years consisted solely of the survey.

The table is organized alphabetically by country, showcasing progress using official statistics over the years. It demonstrates that more countries were involved with big data in 2024 than in previous years, as indicated by:

- The number of responses regarding the use of big data for official statistics: eight in 2024 compared to 7 in both 2023 and 2022.
- The total number of responses to all structuring questions.
- The overall number of affirmative responses.

Table 3 – Answers to structural questions by year and country

COUNTRIES	Consultation Year			
	2022 (online questionnaire)	2023 (online questionnaire)	2024	
			(online questionnaire)	(in-depth interviews)
Argentina	O/X/E	O/X/E	O/X/E/F	YES
Belize	N	SR	F	SR
Bolivia	SR	O/F	SR	SR
Bonaire	SR	X/E	E/F	YES
Brazil	O/X/E	O/X/E	O/X/E/F	YES
Chile	O/E	SR	X/E/F	YES
Colombia	O/X/E	O/X/E	O/X/E/F	YES
Costa Rica	O/E	E	SR	SR
Cuba	E	E	X/E/F	SR
Curaçao	SR	E	SR	SR
Ecuador	E	O/E	O/E/F	YES
Granada	SR	SR	N	SR
Guatemala	SR	SR	N	YES
Guiana	SR	E	SR	SR
Saint Martin Islands	SR	F	SR	SR
México	X/E	X/E	O/X/E/F	YES
Montserrat	SR	E	SR	SR
Panamá	F	SR	SR	SR
Paraguay	F	O/E	O/X/E/F	YES
Peru	O/E	O/X/E/F	O/X/E/F	YES
Dominican Republic	E	E/F	X/E/F	YES
Suriname	N	SR	SR	SR
Uruguay	O/X/E	X/E	O/X/E/F	YES
Venezuela	F	SR	SR	SR

Source: United Nations Regional Hub for Big Data in Brazil. Internacional Consultation on the use of Big Data in Latin America and the Caribbean, 2022, 2023 and 2024.

Notes: “O” answer for official statistics, “X” answer for experimental statistics, “E” answer for studies or tests, “F” answer for future plans, “N” answer negatively, “SR” without answer e “YES” for countries participating at in-depth interviews.

Notably, in-depth interviews were conducted with all countries that responded affirmatively to all four structuring questions, all of which had positively answered at least two

questions in 2023. This applies to six countries: Argentina, Brazil, Colombia, Mexico, Paraguay, and Uruguay.

From these numbers, it can be inferred that there was an expansion in the use of big data for statistics, as evidenced by the increase in positive responses to the survey from four countries between 2022 and 2024. These figures highlight a trend toward greater engagement with this type of data. Another important observation is the increased involvement of countries, reflected in the higher number of positive responses from 2022 to 2024.

At the bottom of the table, ten countries are noted to have participated in only one consultation. Among these, three countries—Grenada, Guatemala, and Suriname—at some point declared that they do not work in any of the areas related to the structuring questions. In the same group, three other countries—Sint Maarten, Panama, and Venezuela—responded affirmatively only to future plans. These countries have only one response across the three years of consultations, which may indicate a lack of interest in participating in such surveys and a lack of engagement with the topic.

It is worth noting that Argentina, Brazil, Colombia, Mexico, Peru, and Uruguay responded positively to all four structuring questions, with Peru repeating this pattern in 2023 and 2024. Cuba, Ecuador, the Dominican Republic, and Chile also increased their involvement, even without addressing all four areas of the structuring questions.

All countries that responded positively to all four structuring questions, except Cuba, participated in the in-depth interviews. This increase in involvement and the willingness to participate in interviews signify an interest in working on and investing in the topic.

The data analysis from the previous table illustrates the varying levels of engagement by different countries with the topic of big data about the four structuring survey questions. The table below summarizes this engagement to establish a benchmark for growth (or lack thereof) in each structuring question.

Table 4 – Number of countries that answered the Consultation, but year and situation

Status	Consultation Year		
	2022 ⁶	2023 ⁷	2024
Answered the Consultation	16	17	15
Using big data for official statistics	7	7	8
Using big data for experimental statistics	5	8	10
Develop studies or tests to use big data	11	14	12
Have plans to use big data in the future	3	4	12

Source: United Nations Regional Hub for Big Data in Brazil. Internacional Consultation on the use of Big Data in Latin America and the Caribbean, 2022, 2023 and 2024.

A consistent increase in engagement with big data is observed, going beyond specific decisions by individual countries. Plans for using big data stand out as the area with the most significant positive difference, with three times more countries adopting plans from one year to the next.

The structuring questions regarding using big data for official statistics, experimental statistics, studies, and plans were presented in a predefined matrix format of Big Data Types and Topics for its use.

In addition to direct responses within this matrix, the questionnaire also allowed for other combinations to be declared through two supplementary questions. The first question mapped the existence of different combinations using a mandatory closed-ended “yes” or “no” question. The second question accepted optional open-ended responses.

According to United Nations population estimates, in 2023, there were 23 countries in Latin America and the Caribbean with populations exceeding one million. Seven did not respond to any of the consultations. These countries often face high levels of poverty, such as Haiti—the most populous non-responding country—and include Honduras, Nicaragua, El Salvador, Puerto Rico, Jamaica, and Trinidad and Tobago.

Regarding participation in the 2024 Consultation, over 70% of responding countries demonstrated broad engagement with big data, as 11 of the 15 countries answered affirmatively to at least three of the four structuring questions. Of these, ten countries participated in the in-

⁶ Internacional Consultation on the use of Big Data in Latin America and the Caribbean, 2022. UN Regional Hub for Big Data in Brazil, <https://storymaps.arcgis.com/stories/3e42f28257004e4b98b0606518185656>. Access in October 2024.

⁷ Internacional Consultation on the use of Big Data in Latin America and the Caribbean, 2023. UN Regional Hub for Big Data in Brazil, <https://storymaps.arcgis.com/stories/9bc866713dde444eb9888d9983717f62>. Access in October 2024.

depth interviews. Only Cuba did not participate in the interviews but provided responses indicating engagement in three structuring questions.

4.3. Structuring questions

The analyses below follow the order in which the questions appear in the questionnaire, beginning with the tabulated results of the country responses, followed by the open-ended responses. Accordingly, the subsequent sections will present the results for producing official statistics, followed by data on experimental statistics, studies on the use of big data, and plans.

The data will be presented from the perspectives of combinations, types, topics, and open-ended responses for each structuring question.

4.3.1. Official statistics

Eight of the 15 responding countries are engaged in this type of work: Argentina, Brazil, Colombia, Ecuador, Mexico, Paraguay, Peru, and Uruguay. All these countries, except Ecuador, responded affirmatively to all four structuring questions in the survey. This exception does not appear significant, as the question for which Ecuador did not provide a positive response was related to experimental statistics.

Seven countries provided negative responses to this question: Belize, Bonaire, Chile, Cuba, Grenada, Guatemala, and the Dominican Republic.

From the perspective of Big Data Types, "Population" and "Price" were the most utilized, reported by 6 and 5 countries, respectively.

Table 5 – Number of countries producing official statistics with big data, by topic

Topic	Number of countries
Prices	5
Population	6
Agriculture	3
Environment	2
Others	2

Source: United Nations Regional Hub for Big Data in Brazil. Internacional Consultation on the use of Big Data in Latin America and the Caribbean, 2024.

Regarding the most commonly used Types and Topics of big data, Web Scraping was the most frequent for Prices, while Satellite Imagery and Mobile Phone Data were the most common for Population.

Table 6 –Number of countries producing official statistics with big data by topic and type of big data

Type of big data	Topic			
	Prices	Population	Agriculture	Environment
Web scraping	5	1	-	-
Satellite imagery	1	3	3	2
Mobile phone data	1	3	1	-
Scanner data	1	2	-	-
Smart metes	1	2	-	-
Financial transactions	1	-	-	-
Health records	-	1	-	-

Source: United Nations Regional Hub for Big Data in Brazil. Internacional Consultation on the use of Big Data in Latin America and the Caribbean, 2024.

Notably, all countries reporting engagement in official statistics responded positively to at least two other structuring questions. While the structuring questions do not suggest a mandatory progression from involvement in one area to others, the data suggests that this progression aligns with practical trends.

There were 28 mentions of different combinations, and after excluding responses categorized as "Other Types and Topics," 23 distinct combinations remain. The most frequently cited combination was using Web Scraping data for Prices, with four countries (Argentina, Brazil, Mexico, and Uruguay) reporting this Type and Topic pairing. Regarding Topics, Population statistics (10 countries) and Price statistics (8 countries) were the most commonly reported, while Satellite imagery was the most cited Type, mentioned three times and exclusively by Colombia.

It is significant that six countries—Argentina, Brazil, Colombia, Paraguay, Peru, and Uruguay—account for 22 of the 23 mentions of official statistics usage.

Open-ended responses required careful analysis to ensure their relevance to the report. Of the responses from five countries, only two from Colombia were pertinent to this question, highlighting the use of Satellite imagery for various applications that were difficult to classify. Specific applications included support for demographic censuses, social security, statistics on armed conflicts, and criminal records. Another country, Peru, identified "Health Records" and "Energy Consumption" as Types, but these responses did not indicate corresponding Topics.

4.3.2. Experimental statistics

Ten of the 15 responding countries reported producing experimental statistics using big data: Argentina, Brazil, Chile, Colombia, Cuba, Mexico, Paraguay, Peru, the Dominican Republic, and Uruguay. The remaining five countries—Belize, Bonaire, Ecuador, Grenada, and Guatemala—declared they do not engage in experimental statistics.

From the perspective of the number of countries and their use of different Big Data Types, the same pattern observed with official statistics was repeated, where Population and Price emerged as the most common Topics.

Table 7 – Number of countries producing experimental statistics with big data, by topic

Topic	Number of countries
Prices	6
Population	7
Agriculture	1
Environment	4
Others	1

Source: United Nations Regional Hub for Big Data in Brazil. Internacional Consultation on the use of Big Data in Latin America and the Caribbean, 2024.

For Types and Topics, Web Scraping and Prices represent the most commonly used combination by countries, alongside Satellite Imagery and Environment. These two types of big data appear to be the ones countries most easily adapt to.

Table 8 - Number of countries producing experimental statistics with big data by topic and type of big data

Type of big data	Topic			
	Prices	Population	Agriculture	Environment
Web scraping	4	3	-	1
Satellite imagery	-	3	1	4
Mobile phone data	-	1	-	-
Scanner data	1	1	-	-
Smart metes	1	2	-	-
Financial transactions	1	-	-	-
Health records	-	1	-	-

Source: United Nations Regional Hub for Big Data in Brazil. Internacional Consultation on the use of Big Data in Latin America and the Caribbean, 2024.

When analyzing the responses regarding the production of experimental statistics using big data, the following combinations stand out: Colombia reported five combinations, while Paraguay and Peru reported three each, making them the countries with the highest variety of experimental statistics combinations.

It is also observed that there were 24 mentions of combinations of Big Data Types and Topics, a slightly higher number than for official statistics, excluding combinations categorized as "Other Types and Topics." The most cited combinations were Web Scraping and Prices and Satellite Imagery and Environment, with four mentions.

Notably, nine countries provided positive responses regarding using experimental statistics, the highest among all the structuring questions. Argentina was among them. The section of the questionnaire on official statistics had already indicated producing experimental statistics for prices based on financial transactions. This response could have been mapped through the matrix of Types and Topics. Furthermore, Argentina highlighted using online commerce data in the open-ended question about experimental statistics.

Additionally, Argentina, Brazil, Colombia, Mexico, and Uruguay reported producing economic statistics through Web Scraping, Financial Transactions, and Online Commerce, citing Big Data Types more specifically. Chile highlighted using Metadata for demographic statistics, while Cuba pointed to a related purpose—demographic statistics.

Colombia and Uruguay also mentioned numerous purposes involving other Types and Topics but did not provide combinations compatible with the matrix, i.e., they did not specify Type and Topic pairs. Their responses included using Machine Learning for Natural Language Processing, Satellite Imagery for SDGs (without specifying which ones), Facebook Data for discrimination predictors, and LinkedIn Data to analyze female participation in the labor force.

While there is a noticeable prevalence of big data usage in economic areas such as prices, labor market activity, and the economy, Colombia's responses stood out for their diversity and innovation compared to other countries.

4.3.3. Studies on the use of big data

Regarding studies on the use of big data in statistical production, the table below illustrates the number of countries by Big Data Type, showing that Population and Prices were the most common topics. A total of 12 countries reported conducting such studies.

Table 9 - Number of countries developing studies or tests to use big data, by topic

Topic	Number of countries
Prices	6
Population	10
Agriculture	5
Environment	7
Others	2

Source: United Nations Regional Hub for Big Data in Brazil. Internacional Consultation on the use of Big Data in Latin America and the Caribbean, 2024.

Regarding the responses, 59 combinations of Big Data Types and Topics were suggested, surpassing the 33 combinations identified for experimental statistics. These combinations were proposed by 12 of the 15 countries that reported conducting studies. Belize, Grenada, and Guatemala are the only countries without studies on the use of big data.

The table below summarizes the number of countries that responded to different Big Data Types and Topics. It highlights that Satellite Imagery and Mobile Phone Data were the most common types, paired with the Topics Population and Agriculture. Conversely, Web Scraping also showed significant adoption.

Table 10 - Number of countries developing studies or tests to use big data by topic and type of big data

Type of big data	Topic			
	Prices	Population	Agriculture	Environment
Web scraping	4	4	2	3
Satellite imagery	1	5	5	4
Mobile phone data	1	5	1	1
Scanner data	2	1	-	-
Smart metes	-	4	1	-
Financial transactions	1	1	-	-
Health records	-	3	-	-

Source: United Nations Regional Hub for Big Data in Brazil. Internacional Consultation on the use of Big Data in Latin America and the Caribbean, 2024.

Seven countries suggested new combinations regarding responses about other types and topics. Once again, some were not utilized as the text did not allow them to align with the question's objective. The incorporated combinations include Mexico's use of satellite imagery for economic activity and web scraping to measure the digital economy.

Beyond the number of countries, it is notable that some combinations were cited multiple times by respondents. The Topic Population was mentioned 24 times, predominantly

by Cuba and Peru (5 times each), followed by Brazil (4 times). The second most cited topic was Prices, which was mentioned 10 times. It is worth noting that no other Topic was cited with the same intensity by any country as Population.

Chile mentioned using Mobile Device Metadata for research, although it did not specify the corresponding Topic. Peru cited its use for various topics, including population, agriculture, labor market, poverty, and inequality, but it did not specify the Big Data Type.

Colombia and Uruguay reiterated the same Topics they had mentioned for experimental statistics. Colombia noted the use of Web Scraping for analyzing discrimination and introduced a new application for School Accessibility without specifying the Big Data Type. Uruguay cited Mobility using Mobile Phone Data and e-commerce data for Price Indicators.

4.3.4. Future plans for using big data

Thirteen of the 15 countries reported plans to use big data. Only two countries—Grenada and Guatemala—did not intend to use big data to produce statistics.

Given that the question pertained to planning, nearly all respondents answered affirmatively, regardless of whether countries could implement those plans. The table below summarizes the countries’ responses.

The table also highlights the most commonly cited Topics. In addition to population, which was the most mentioned, there was a balance between agriculture, prices, and the environment. Many countries frequently cited all four, with only a few references to other Topics.

Table 11 - Number of countries with plans to use big data, by topic

Topic	Number of countries
Prices	7
Population	10
Agriculture	8
Environment	7
Others	3

Source: United Nations Regional Hub for Big Data in Brazil. Internacional Consultation on the use of Big Data in Latin America and the Caribbean, 2024.

Regarding the combinations of Types and Topics, most countries cite Satellite Imagery combined with Agriculture and Population.

Table 12 - Number of countries with plans to use big data by topic and type of big data

Type of big data	Topic			
	Prices	Population	Agriculture	Environment
Web scraping	5	4	3	2
Satellite imagery	2	7	8	5
Mobile phone data	2	5	1	2
Scanner data	2	-	-	-
Smart metres	-	3	1	-
Financial transactions	1	2	-	-
Health records	1	-	-	-
Web scraping	-	2	-	-

Source: United Nations Regional Hub for Big Data in Brazil. Internacional Consultation on the use of Big Data in Latin America and the Caribbean, 2024.

More than 60 combinations of Big Data Types and Topics to be utilized or developed in the future were submitted, 60 of which corresponded to existing combinations in the matrix, while five countries suggested new combinations.

Regarding Big Data Types, there is a repeated preference for Population, leading with 24 mentions, followed by Prices and Agriculture, with 13 mentions, and finally Environment, cited 10 times. Since these Topics were the most mentioned across the three previous questions, there is potential for exchanging experiences. What is a plan for some countries is already official or experimental statistics for others.

Open-ended responses suggesting other Types and Topics were limited, provided by five countries: Argentina, Colombia, Cuba, Ecuador, the Dominican Republic, and Uruguay.

After evaluation, the recorded responses were from Colombia and the Dominican Republic. While the Dominican Republic focused on integrating Satellite Imagery and Drones, Colombia demonstrated a greater diversity of interests. The cited Topics were related to the SDGs, Economic Activity, Discrimination Indicators, Migration, and Territorial Planning, although no specific Big Data Types were indicated.

4.4. Final questions of the survey

The questionnaire was structured in two parts. The first part has been discussed, focusing on structuring questions. The second part included the following questions, which will be explored below:

- Does the Statistical Institute have any resources or expertise in using big data that can be shared with other countries? If so, what are they?
- What are the limitations and needs for using big data in statistical production in your country?
- Indicate the training topics of most significant interest or immediate need.
- Do you have any additional suggestions to help the Hub plan actions to support using big data in the region?

4.4.1. Resources or expertise to share

Of the 15 countries that responded to the 2024 Consultation, 5 (Belize, Cuba, Grenada, Guatemala, and Peru) reported no resources or expertise to share.

Countries that responded positively presented considerably varied resources or expertise. As the table below summarizes, this diversity indicates the potential for sharing practices, experiences, work methods, and data processing techniques among countries.

Declarations about resources or expertise to share did not always align with the matrix model of Big Data Types and Topics. Sometimes, the suggestions were based on the type of big data, while in other cases, they referred to its application or the results achieved.

The following table summarizes the primary resources and expertise to be shared.

Table 13 – Resources to share, by country

Country	Resources
Argentina	Work with patent indices and georeferenced data.
Brazil	Web scraping, remote sensing, satellite imagery, and coding with artificial intelligence.
Chile	Generation of nowcasting indicators using mobile device metadata for field research.
Ecuador	Big data processing.
México	Indicators derived from satellite imagery.
Paraguay	Use of big data with artificial intelligence.
Dominican Republic	Monitoring of sargassum through satellite and drone imagery.

Uruguay	Establishing partnerships for data access.
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Source: United Nations Regional Hub for Big Data in Brazil. Internacional Consultation on the use of Big Data in Latin America and the Caribbean, 2024.

The diversity of experiences includes new Topics, such as the Patent Index and Sargassum Monitoring. The Big Data Types involved often include Satellite Imagery or Georeferenced Data, which appeared consistently in responses to the structuring questions.

While Artificial Intelligence is not categorized as a Type or Topic, it is a critical data processing technique. McFeely's definition at the beginning of this report highlights that it is equally significant for this work.

Combining countries' experiences or expertise with their plans offers a pathway to enhance work in this area in upcoming years.

4.4.2. Limitations and needs for the use of big data

Needs were presented through open-ended responses, which were analyzed and classified. Not all countries provided suggestions; notably, this group aligns with those that did not report experience with the topic, namely Grenada, Guatemala, and Peru.

The question emphasized identifying both limitations and needs. The responses primarily addressed needs, interpreted as areas where limitations exist and support is required to use big data. These areas, ranked by incidence, are presented in the following table.

Table 14 – Number of countries and limitations for use of big data, by each limitation

Limitations	Number of countries
Skilled personnel and training	7
Technological infrastructure	6
Legislation for access to big data	3
Access to big data sources, such as mobile phone	2
Cooperation between public and private institutions	1
Accountability for citizens regarding data access security	1
Data visualization techniques to facilitate understanding	1
Big data literacy	1

Source: United Nations Regional Hub for Big Data in Brazil. Internacional Consultation on the use of Big Data in Latin America and the Caribbean, 2024.

Seven countries suggested two topics, representing more than half of the respondents, considering that three of the 15 countries did not respond to most of the questions. The most

cited areas were Skilled Personnel, training, and Technological Infrastructure, mentioned by seven and six countries, respectively.

At this point, it is essential to clarify that "Skilled Personnel" and "Training" are distinct, though closely related, concepts. The term "Skilled Personnel" refers to the existence of teams equipped with the necessary skills to work with big data, whereas "Training" pertains to providing educational opportunities to develop such skills.

Technological Infrastructure, cited six times, refers to access to computational resources. Given the nature of big data, it is unsurprising that this element appears so frequently, reflecting the need for data processing resources specific to big data.

The third most mentioned item, cited by three countries, was Legislation, which relates to access to big data sources. The fourth item, mentioned by two countries, was Institutional Cooperation, with one additional mention. These three themes are interconnected, pointing to the need for legal frameworks. Legislation refers to ensuring legally secure access to big data, such as mobile phone records or other data from public and private institutions. Similarly, Institutional Cooperation aligns with the broader theme, as it depends on agreements and establishing legal frameworks to access data.

Three additional topics were each mentioned by one country:

1. Data Clarity and Anonymity to ensure responsible data usage.
2. Investment in Visualization Techniques to improve data comprehension and engagement.
3. Understanding the Concept of Big Data, as the lack of a unified definition creates challenges in focusing efforts effectively. Improving clarity on what constitutes big data could streamline technical and research efforts.

4.4.3. Training topics of greatest interest

All 12 responding countries provided suggestions on training topics. The suggestions encompassed specific big data types and the skills needed to handle big data. Due to the diverse responses, a categorization system was applied to organize the various competencies and skills mentioned.

Suggested Skills

Countries identified the following tools and techniques for analysis:

- - Applications: Tableau, Power BI, Spark R, and Python.
- - Techniques: Data mining, security and privacy, artificial intelligence, and machine learning.

The applications were grouped as tools for data analysis. At the same time, the techniques were categorized as broader competencies, such as using artificial intelligence, addressing security and privacy concerns, and performing data mining tasks.

Suggested Data Types and Topics for Training included:

- Natural Language Processing
- Web Scraping for Prices
- Mobile Data for Mobility
- Scanner Data for Prices
- Remote Sensing for Population and Agriculture
- Big Data Applications for Census and Surveys
- Satellite Imagery and Navigation Data

The training demands reflected varying levels of team development and experience, highlighting areas where expertise is sought.

4.4.4. Contributions to help the Hub plan actions

Four countries (Argentina, Guatemala, Paraguay, and Peru) did not provide suggestions for the Hub to plan or support big data usage.

Six countries mentioned the most common contribution as a request for training and workshops. Following this, experience exchange was also suggested, often in conjunction with training.

Training suggestions were framed as the Hub's need to promote these opportunities, connecting them to the organization of in-person events and presentations.

Additionally, experience exchange, mentioned by six countries (twice alongside training), was described as an opportunity for disseminating best practices. Such events were seen as a means to accelerate learning by fostering peer-to-peer knowledge sharing.

A particularly notable example came from Chile, which detailed its collaboration with Mexico (INEGI) on a Data Lake project. This partnership was presented as a case study for the Hub, highlighting best practices in cooperative work. Interestingly, despite being a respondent to the 2024 Consultation, Mexico did not mention this collaboration, potentially due to the choice of respondents for the survey.

Preliminary Insights from the Final Questions

Analyzing the responses by country suggests that the more advanced a country is in using big data, the more specific its needs become. For instance, Brazil, Mexico, and the Dominican Republic commonly highlighted personnel and technological infrastructure needs.

Reflecting on these findings, McFeely's (2019) observation remains relevant: *"Finally, big data may offer the UN an opportunity to exercise some leadership and regain some control over an increasingly congested and rapidly fragmenting information space."* This perspective underscores the United Nations' potential role in fostering big data initiatives. Strengthening national statistical institutes (NSIs) could serve as a tangible step toward asserting this leadership.

5. Results from in-depth interviews

The in-depth interviews were conducted using a script (Appendix B) developed based on the online survey questionnaire but without the intention of replicating it. The script consisted of structuring questions (Item 5.1) related to using big data to produce official statistics, experimental statistics, studies, and plans for using big data in developing statistics. It also included a second group, referred to in this report as final questions (Item 5.2), which mapped the use of big data for other purposes, resources required for its use, and experiences to be shared with different institutes. Once finalized, the script was tested in two interviews with informants from a national statistical institute. The results were discussed by the project implementation team, which prompted adjustments. The suggested adjustments were minor, and once finalized, the Portuguese version of the script was translated into two additional languages for the interviews: English and Spanish.

The interviews were conducted following electronic invitations sent to representatives of national statistical institutions by the UN Regional Hub for Big Data in Brazil. The recipients were representatives from the national statistical institutes of all countries participating in at

least one of the previous surveys (2022, 2023, or 2024). Using this criterion, 24 countries were identified. As responses to the invitations were received, the in-depth interviews were scheduled.

The scheduling process involved the following steps:

- Sending an introductory email to establish initial contact and present the interview team.
- Explaining the purpose of the interview and its contextual framework.
- Sharing a summary of the script.
- Sending the country's most recent response to previous surveys.

As a clarification, sharing these materials and information was to help the point of contact at the respective national statistical institute (NSI) better prepare for the interview. For the coordination team, this preparation allowed the NSIs to identify individuals most suited to address the topic, gather relevant information, and contribute more effectively to the in-depth interview.

Once the materials and information were sent, the process advanced to scheduling a date and time suitable for the teams. The interviews were conducted via the Zoom videoconferencing platform and recorded on the cloud, with the link shared in advance after confirming the schedule. The recordings were then transcribed verbatim, preserving the exact dynamics of the interview.

Since the interviews followed a script, responses did not always align directly with the corresponding questions. During their answers, respondents often recalled elements related to other questions or preemptively addressed topics from upcoming questions.

Subsequently, the transcripts were reviewed, with responses organized to address the intent of each question specifically. This review process resulted in a refined dataset summarized in data sheets (Appendix C).

Given the project's design, two months were allocated to complete all interviews. This included identifying eligible countries, sending invitations, receiving responses, scheduling, and conducting the interviews. The time between sending the invitation and receiving a response was outside the governance of the project team. A lack of response from a country could indicate disinterest or a delay. As time progressed, follow-up invitations were sent to non-responding countries. In total, 13 countries expressed interest in participating. Of these, one country declined after canceling two scheduled interviews, and two countries explicitly indicated they were not interested in participating.

Finally, once the interviews were conducted and transcribed, the responses were divided into individual content units for categorization and tabulation. This tabulation helped organize the responses and capture narratives illustrating practices developed by different countries. The table below presents the interview schedule by participating countries, listed alphabetically. Appendix D details the interviewed professionals, their respective roles, and their countries.

Table 15 – Date and duration of interviews by country

Country	Date	Duration
Argentina	July 24 th	00h32m06s
Bonaire	September 11 th	01h03m32s
Brazil	July 9 th	00h40m59s
Chile	July 10 th	00h54m16s
Colombia	July 17 th	00h54m05s
Ecuador	August 14 th	01h20m51s
Guatemala	July 26 th	00h38m32s
México	July 11 th	01h10m00s
Paraguay	July 13 th	00h49m37s
Peru	July 31 th	00h54m20s
Dominicana Republic	July 16 th	00h47m59s
Uruguay	July 10 th	00h57m04s

Source: United Nations Regional Hub for Big Data in Brazil. Internacional Consultation on the use of Big Data in Latin America and the Caribbean, 2024.

5.1. Structuring questions

The 2024 Consultation utilized multiple data collection instruments. In addition to the online questionnaire, in-depth interviews were conducted, enabling a more detailed examination of what countries were implementing.

Two researchers conducted the interviews simultaneously: one led the discussion while the other monitored the script to ensure no questions or topics were skipped. This model was adopted due to the challenges of scheduling interviews with national teams and to maximize the effectiveness of these activities.

During the interviews, the researchers asked follow-up questions when necessary, seeking examples, clarification on the Types or Topics being addressed, the cost of production, and the partnerships involved, whether governmental or private.

The primary task regarding the responses from the in-depth interviews was categorization. This was guided by two primary considerations: The first was aligning with the

items from the online questionnaire, particularly the Big Data Types and Topics, and the second was allowing categorization beyond the questionnaire's predefined items to capture the richness of the collected testimonies.

The tables summarizing the categorized responses were organized alphabetically by rows and columns. Cells without numerical information indicate either zero responses or no declarations.

5.1.1. Official statistics

Seven countries spontaneously mentioned producing statistics using big data. Examples of such work referred to large-volume data linked to administrative records and census data, which were integrated with data from other national government sectors. However, while demonstrating the combination of datasets with different structures and highlighting the challenges faced by national statistical institute teams, these examples did not exhibit one of the key characteristics of big data: velocity.

Identifying administrative data as big data appears straightforward but depends not only on the definition of big data itself. This intersects with the idea of statistical and big data literacy, a topic Abbas (2023) raised in research involving IT human resources in Pakistan's public sector organizations. Understanding the concept of big data and sharing a common perspective on it can influence perceptions of its use. The same study offers an interesting big data mapping framework, proposing scales for the three Vs (Volume, Velocity, and Variety). These scales invite readers to reflect on each criterion—for instance: Is data production frequency for big data considered annual, monthly, or daily? Does volume refer to less than 1 gigabyte, between 1 and 10 gigabytes, or more than 10 gigabytes? Such questions help contextualize some countries' claims of utilizing big data, even when their data does not meet the criteria defined in this work. This reflects that big data is a contested concept, with variations in the number of Vs suggested in the literature.

A United Nations Working Group document (2013) discussing the relationship between official statistics and big data provides relevant definitions. It highlights the qualities of administrative data that are similar to big data but also emphasizes their limitations. These distinctions offer insight into the selection criteria used in this study.

Traditionally, it has been received, often from public administrations, processed, stored, managed, and used by the NSOs in a very structured manner. Can one consider administrative data “Big” per the definition above? For the moment, the response would probably not be. Administrative data can

become “Big” when the velocity increases, e.g., using extensive administrative data where data is collected daily or weekly instead of the usual once a year or once a month. (Nações Unidas, 2013, p.3).

Relating the survey responses to the statements from the in-depth interviews, it becomes evident that there is a significant alignment between the two. The eight countries that reported using big data for official statistics in the survey also confirmed this during the in-depth interviews. These countries are Argentina, Brazil, Colombia, Ecuador, Mexico, Paraguay, Peru, and Uruguay. However, Brazil and Mexico were the only ones that provided concrete examples of using big data to produce official statistics. In Brazil's case, the use of web scraping for price index production was highlighted. In the interviewee's words:

Atualmente estão em produção, dados, pra passagens aéreas e dados também para transporte por aplicativo. Esses dois é que já tiveram de iniciar alguma coleta, e então, enfim, sendo utilizados parcialmente ou totalmente. Então isso você me perguntou: desde quando a gente começou a estudar isso, acho que pro caso de passagens aéreas em dois mil e dezessete e dezoito e entrou em implantação em 2020, transporte por aplicativo também foi dois mil e dezoito e dezanove. Também entrou em produção em 2020.

Mexico, in turn, produced official statistics using big data until access to data from X (formerly Twitter) was blocked. This experience is noteworthy, as it highlights the production of official statistics with big data and the country's expertise in executing such tasks. Mexico's experience involved sentiment analysis through the daily processing of tweets.

El primer ejemplo que tenemos que trata de ya este más de 8 años, es un ejercicio que hicimos procesando redes sociales, información en redes sociales. ¿qué momento era la red social Twitter. en donde generamos un proceso para poder captar todos. Los tweets que podíamos captar, que se publican en territorio mexicano a partir de la referenciación de estos tweets y hacíamos desarrollarnos un mecanismo de análisis de sentimientos. Esos tweets, entonces generábamos un índice de positividad basado en esos. En ese análisis de sentimientos. Ese era un producto que se publicaba se actualizaba diariamente todos los días. Se publicaba el dato de la mañana, se publicaba el dato del día anterior. Porque todo el proceso era totalmente automatizado desde la captación, el análisis y la publicación. Todo era totalmente automatizado y habrán pasado porque, desafortunadamente, por las nuevas políticas de X. Ahora pues ya no tenemos ese flujo de datos que teníamos antes. Y entonces el proyecto ya tiene un año que ya no se actualiza, no ya este.

Nevertheless, Mexico has been conducting a series of projects using satellite images from the National Aeronautics and Space Administration (NASA) since 1984, which qualify under the concept of big data and official statistics. It is noteworthy that, using the same structure and data, various indices and information are produced for public consumption, such as the Vegetation or Vegetative Cover Index, calculated throughout the year, and the Surface Water Classification Index, which helps assess water access and flood risks.

Five countries have also declared that they do not use big data to produce official statistics: Bonaire, Chile, Guatemala, and the Dominican Republic. Among those countries that reported producing official statistics with big data, some described experiences involving the use of administrative data and its integration with databases from other agencies, census data processing, and combining datasets or even updating cadastral records, such as Argentina, Colombia, Ecuador, Mexico, Paraguay, and Peru. Four countries declared that they do not produce official statistics using big data, namely Bonaire, Chile, Guatemala, and the Dominican Republic.

5.1.2. Experimental statistics

Based on spontaneous responses, three countries declared having no experience producing experimental statistics: Argentina, Bonaire, Guatemala, and Paraguay. Additionally, Ecuador reported an interrupted experience following changes in the data access policy of the X platform (formerly Twitter). The remaining seven countries provided descriptions of work involving big data for the production of experimental statistics.

The most frequently used types of big data were satellite images and web scraping. Reports on using satellite images mainly revolved around vegetation indices, vegetative cover, urbanization, and the availability of open spaces in cities.

From the perspective of topics where big data is utilized, statistics related to economic activity are the most common. These include analyses of different product prices, the calculation of sector-specific GDP, economic activity, or labor market participation of specific groups.

The monitoring of Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) was rarely mentioned during the interviews. Concerning experimental statistics derived from the processing of satellite images, Colombia referenced SDGs 9.1.1 (infrastructure in rural areas), 11.1.1 (access to public transport), 11.3.1 (population dynamics), and 11.7.1 (public spaces in cities).

La estimación de indicadores ODS. Sí, digamos que eso es un proyecto que en el que danés viene trabajando hace muchos años. Empezamos con la estimación del indicador 9.1.1, y en este momento, aparte ese indicador el DANE ha estimado el indicador 11.1 que es acceso a transporte público. Si no estoy mal, el 11.3.1 y el 11.7.1, el 11.7.1 que es espacios abiertos y el 11. Tres. Uno, que es relación entre consumo de tierra y dinámica poblacional. Si no estoy mal. Son estos 4 indicadores y nosotros, pues, hemos hecho todo. La obtención de las imágenes satelitales, los algoritmos de machine learning para poder interpretarlas y algunas modificaciones a la a las metodologías que tiene ONU Habitat que es la agencia custodia (Colombia)

Using the same type of big data, the Dominican Republic experiments with free satellite images (Google Maps) to calculate green areas in the Santo Domingo zone and with NASA images to monitor areas affected by the sargassum phenomenon along the country's coastal regions.

Mexico has conducted a series of projects using NASA satellite images since 1984. Notably, various indices and public information are produced using the same structure and data, such as the Vegetation or Vegetative Cover Index, calculated throughout the year, and the Surface Water Classification Index, which helps assess water access and flood risks. Other projects in Mexico involve experimental statistics and satellite imagery to identify football fields, their quantity and layout, roads, and types of pavement.

Ya estamos usando imágenes que no son gratuitas de alta resolución. Este también es un estudio experimental que tenemos actualmente, en donde estamos viendo. Si podemos utilizar algoritmos de inteligencia artificial para identificación de objetos en imágenes. Solución para poder completar, poder complementar un inventario nacional de infraestructura, identificar elementos de infraestructura que es muy amplio. Esto no. Por ejemplo, nosotros estamos evaluando algoritmos de inteligencia artificial para poder identificar canchas. Esta infraestructura para para la para la actividad deportiva.

Colombia reported starting an experiment to measure women's access to the labor market using LinkedIn web scraping: "The team at the department has a web scraping project to capture information about companies and business statistical records. An exploratory exercise is underway on LinkedIn to measure women's participation in science and technology activities."

Brazil and Mexico indicated that they have experimental statistics projects involving sentiment analysis using data retrieved from social networks. In Mexico's case, this data was used to create a positivity index that was updated daily until access to data from X (formerly Twitter) was restricted.

El primer ejemplo que tenemos que trata de ya este más de 8 años, es un ejercicio que hicimos procesando redes sociales, información en redes sociales. ¿qué momento era la red social Twitter. en donde generamos un proceso para poder captar todos. Los tweets que podíamos captar, que se publican en territorio mexicano a partir de la referenciación de estos tweets y hacíamos desarrollarnos un mecanismo de análisis de sentimientos. Esos tweets, entonces generábamos un índice de positividad basado en esos. En ese análisis de sentimientos. Ese era un producto que se publicaba se actualizaba diariamente todos los días. Se publicaba el dato de la mañana, se publicaba el dato del día anterior. Porque todo el proceso era totalmente automatizado desde la captación, el análisis y la publicación. Todo era totalmente automatizado y habrán pasado porque, desafortunadamente, por las nuevas políticas de X. Ahora pues ya no tenemos ese flujo de datos que teníamos antes. Y entonces el proyecto ya tiene un año que ya no se actualiza, no ya este. (Mexico)

Uruguay has a project utilizing Google satellite images to update the building registry and built-up area, specifying the number of floors.

Usamos un proyecto que se llama open buildings que ellos desarrollaron un algoritmo con inteligencia artificial que interpreta las imágenes satelitales y transforma cada edificación en un polígono y eso, bueno, eso es público. Entonces, descargamos esos polígonos y nos permite asociarlos con nuestro catastro. Y bueno, Eso sí, son Ahí tenemos estadísticas experimentales, porque de hecho tenemos un dashboard... contabilizamos, por ejemplo, una superficie edificada en todo el país, por provincia.

Regarding experimental statistics, some practices have the potential to transition into the realm of official statistics, such as monitoring SDGs, mapping green or flood-prone areas, or conducting sentiment analysis. In some cases, data access can pose a barrier to such initiatives, as seen with specific social networks that limit access by charging for data. In other cases, the availability of free satellite images can facilitate the enhancement of practices, enabling the development of skilled professionals, the establishment of enduring institutional frameworks, and the promotion of algorithms, techniques, and visualizations to support public sector decision-making—a critical role of official statistics. This highlights the potential for sustained efforts to cultivate teams that advance the use and adoption of this data type by national statistical institutes.

5.1.3. Studies on the use of big data

In-depth interviews confirmed the trend identified in the 2024 survey. As questions required less investment in human resources, techniques, and technological resources, the number of positive responses increased. The same pattern was observed when comparing positive responses about the use of experimental statistics and studies on big data. In total, seven countries—Brazil, Chile, Colombia, Ecuador, Mexico, the Dominican Republic, and Uruguay—reported conducting studies on the use of big data.

Argentina, Bonaire, Guatemala, and Peru either declared they had no studies on big data usage or that their studies did not involve big data. Paraguay claimed to use big data, but the examples provided—despite involving large databases and machine learning—did not qualify as big data sources.

The most commonly used types of big data in studies were satellite images, used by Brazil, Chile, Colombia, and Mexico, and web scraping, used by Brazil, Mexico, the Dominican Republic, and Uruguay. Brazil and Mexico appeared in both categories, utilizing satellite images for studies estimating agricultural production but applying web scraping for entirely different purposes. Brazil used web scraping for pricing data on cars, electronics, medications, and lodging. At the same time, Mexico applied natural language processing to news articles to assess violence intensity in specific territories and forced displacement.

Hay otra línea, pero también este, aprovechar las noticias de la en Internet para medir, pues, digamos, la intensidad de ciertos fenómenos: México, desafortunadamente, tenemos problemas de violencia, no de desplazamiento forzado. Hay comunidades que se ven las personas forzadas a salir por el tema de la violencia. Entonces a través de las noticias poder identificar la intensidad. Aquí no estamos hablando tanto de cuántos desplazados Eso es muy difícil de medir con las noticias, pero sí podemos medir qué tan intenso es la presencia la violencia en los territorios. (Mexico)

Similarly, the Dominican Republic conducted studies using mobile phone data to model human mobility in response to natural disasters.

Studies on prices were noted in the Dominican Republic (via web scraping), Mexico, and Brazil (via access to fiscal receipts), requiring agreements with other sectors for data access and subsequent processing.

Dados de notas fiscais pra índice de preço. Secretaria de Fazenda, que são os profissionais da base. Não sei se a Receita Federal não é. Algo poderia fazer esse acordo tão mais recentemente, tem havido conversas nesse sentido com algumas secretarias. Tem tido alguma aproximação. E a gente tá aguardando pra ver se a gente consegue avançar nessas negociações e ter um acesso mais robusto a essas bases.

In Mexico, a similar study was conducted through agreements with banking institutions.

Y otra línea de productos son también aprovechar datos de instituciones privadas. Actualmente tenemos convenios con bancos privados que nos dan información agregada sobre sobre ingreso y consumo de tarjeta. Entonces podemos hacer estadística a nivel municipal sobre sobre este tipo de datos, que es también información muy, muy rica, con un alto nivel de frecuencia y de desagregación. Digo, a nivel municipal, pues es bastante, bastante bueno.

Brazil mentioned web scraping practices for gathering pricing data on essential goods.

In their words:

A gente tem feito estudos também, né? Com outros setores da cesta (básica) via webscraping. Então a gente tem tentado pra expandir ou avaliar a possibilidade de expandir pra outros setores. A gente tem coletado atualmente ou tentado coletar informações de automóveis novos e usados. Estava tentando coletar informações sobre hospedagem, locação de veículos, medicamentos, de eletrônicos. ...todos esses casos por webscraping.

Several noteworthy examples exist of the use of satellite images. Mexico and Brazil used these images to estimate agricultural production, as highlighted by a Brazilian interviewee.

Um trabalho bacana sendo desenvolvido pelo pessoal da área do agro. Então o uso de imagens de satélite pra avaliação de área cultivada no que está sendo cultivado. E acho que tinha uma coisa também de rotas de otimização de rotas. Então acho que isso é um. São estudos que têm sido desenvolvidos

An interesting application of satellite images was noted in Chile, aimed at wildfire prediction.

Pero, bueno, estamos trabajando ahora con Modis (satélite da Nasa) y el ejercicio concreto es la construcción de un clasificador, hecho con redes neuronales, una arquitectura que se llama LCM⁸, y estamos intentando predecir incendios a partir de imágenes históricas. Entonces, usando un periodo de tiempo de 10 días. De imágenes de 10 días. Tratamos de predecir la probabilidad de incendio del día siguiente

Reports on studies using big data, like experimental statistics, primarily involve a few data types, namely satellite images and web scraping. While data access naturally directs technical efforts towards these types, the repetition of practices may also relate to the availability of experienced professionals, documented procedures, articles, and other resources that promote using these big data types, shortening the learning curve for data processing and analysis.

5.1.4. Future plans for using big data

Ten out of the 12 countries interviewed declared future plans for using big data. Only Paraguay and Uruguay responded negatively to this question or suggested actions that did not constitute big data use. At times, responses were not considered as they were more aligned with plans for national statistical institutes to begin working with big data rather than actual usage plans. Examples include suggestions for increasing infrastructure capacity or changing legislation.

Regarding declared plans, interviews often identified multiple types of big data within each country's plans. Chile indicated plans to work with satellite images, consumption meters, and web scraping, while Argentina expressed interest in satellite images, scanner data, and mobile phone data.

⁸ Land Change Modeler, tool for analyzing changes between maps of land use and cover, generated on different dates.

Given the numerous declared plans, it is helpful to categorize them by topic or type. In terms of topics, diversity was significant, ranging from measuring Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) to migration, for example. Argentina mentioned plans to update administrative databases for household surveys using satellite images, similar to plans in Chile and Guatemala, as evidenced by the Argentine interview:

Argentina also mentioned using mobile phone data for mobility, Bonaire cited it for monitoring the tourism sector in specific areas, and Mexico expressed interest in using this data for research projects. Bonaire illustrates the specificity of mobile phone data usage well.

We have not come too well-using telecom data because of the laws and the difficulties. Another thing that comes to my mind, I do not know if that is also an issue in Bonaire, is the situation in Venezuela, so I know that there are many refugees from Venezuela. It isn't easy to get a clear picture. How many? I do not know if they also come to Bonaire. It is more challenging to go to Bonaire than to Curacao. But I agree there are a lot of refugees in Aruba and Curacao, and you can see the migration, I think, also with the telecom data. That is the idea.

Web scraping was the most frequently mentioned item, with six references related to price estimators in Chile or identifying the number of economic units to supplement the national registry in Mexico. Similarly, financial statistics, such as economic activity and price indices, were shared plans among Chile, Colombia, Ecuador, Mexico, and Peru.

Nos gustaría tener acceso a la información que producen las grandes cadenas. Nosotros, qué hacemos ahora? Vamos y recogemos los datos. Pero si entramos a Internet, ahí podemos ver las grandes cadenas de supermercados están en Internet los precios, porque hay que verlo mecanismo, como hago para recopilar toda esa información y tener otra manera de poder obtenerlo con precios? ¿no? Y así podemos ir sacando muchas cosas más. No. (Peru)

Brazil shared a similar focus, indicating plans to work on price statistics through access to fiscal receipts.

O IBGE está tentando avançar, então, sim, isso meio que tentar marcar o máximo de fonte possível mais do nosso lado de estatística de preço. Se a gente conseguir avançar inicialmente dessa parte de uso de notas fiscais pra explorar melhor os dados e tentar adiante com os estudos. Eu acho que esse é o um dos pontos principais que a gente tem como norte atualmente. Tentar ver até onde se a gente consegue avançar, explorar o potencial, ver até onde a gente consegue. Com essa base, se é possível realmente produzir estatísticas

Chile expressed intent to use satellite images for rural economic activities.

También hay un proyecto que está intentando hacer: un Landcover, que básicamente es un mapa de uso de suelo con la finalidad de generar marcos de muestreo para descuentas agropecuarias, pero también a partir de las mismas técnicas, poder estimar intensidad de producción de ciertos cultivos

y algunos usos de ese tipo. Eso también se está desarrollando, pero aún no está concluido.

Argentina aimed to use satellite images to update administrative household databases, demonstrating thematic diversification with the same type of big data: “también la actualización de los domicilios, si, el archivo de domicilios a partir de registros administrativos o imágenes satelitales.”

Mexico mentioned a noteworthy plan related to information and experience sharing involving the creation of an incubator to transition experimental products to production stages.

Cosas que tenemos en la perspectiva como algo importante a consolidar. Es este proceso de poder llevar los productos que ya tenemos en una fase experimental, una incubadora, poderlos sacar de la incubadora y llevar a las áreas productivas, y que, ya sean parte de los procesos productivos. Eso es algo que tenemos, digamos, en el corto plazo. Ya estamos trabajando en ello porque digo 1 lo puede hacer una vez y puede tener éxito. Pero si eso no está debidamente institucionalizado, pues puede ser algo pues anecdótico. ¿no? Entonces lo que necesitamos es tener un proceso institucionalizado para poder hacer estas transferencias de innovaciones tecnológicas, poderlas, incorporar a los procesos productivos. Eso es algo que en lo que estamos actualmente trabajando para poderlo llevar a cabo en el futuro este cercano. (Mexico)

Regarding the Topics, five countries—Argentina, Brazil, Chile, Ecuador, and Peru—mentioned the development of price indices, while economic activity was cited twice. The Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) were related to urbanization, specifically SDG 11.

Future plans for using big data may have been presented as aspirations, perceived interests, or potential pathways stemming from institutional efforts toward this objective.

5.2. Final questions from in-depth interviews

The in-depth interviews included questions similar to those in the second part of the 2024 survey. These questions were divided into two areas: using big data for purposes other than direct statistics production and the resources required and available for using big data.

While the first area aimed to capture uses of big data supporting other statistics, the second involved two questions derived from pretesting to ensure precise, focused queries. The questions were:

- Does your statistical institute/office use big data for purposes other than direct statistics production?
- What resources would be necessary for producing statistics with big data?
- What can you share with other statistical institutes/offices about your experience working with big data?

5.2.1. Use of big data for other purposes

Seven countries reported using big data for purposes other than producing official experimental statistics or studies. These countries were Argentina, Chile, Colombia, Ecuador, Guatemala, Mexico, and Uruguay. These uses were identified through 18 examples. It was not always easy to understand what was meant by the use of big data for other purposes; however, the interview script provided not only an explanation of this definition but also examples, such as using big data as input for planning a sample, which helped respondents identify relevant information.

The declared uses primarily focused on improving field survey planning or refining samples by identifying eligible households. Examples include Argentina, Ecuador, and Uruguay, where energy consumption records were used to compare survey samples to avoid wasting resources visiting abandoned locations or planning the national census. Uruguay's report clearly illustrates this use of big data.

Accedemos a datos de consumo de energía eléctrica. La empresa. Hay una sola empresa proveedora de servicio de energía eléctrica en el país y ellos nos dan datos identificado de consumo de energía eléctrica, y eso lo utilizamos como fuente secundaria para chequear datos de encuestas para confirmar datos de encuestas o para seleccionar algunas muestras, lo que son datos de empresas, consumo eléctrico de empresas, con lo que es la producción lo que nos reportan en las encuestas. (Uruguay)

On the other hand, Mexico highlighted the use of big data in census operations, mainly to locate interviewees and analyze geospatial data.

También estamos trabajando actualmente en cómo aprovechar diversas fuentes de información para mejorar la planeación de los operativos, de los de las encuestas y del Censos, no poder poderme medir de mejor manera la eficiencia de los procesos, porque actualmente la eficiencia es cuántas encuestas realizaste en qué tiempo no, pero es igual. Si la encuesta la realizaste al lado de tu casa o en la cuadra, donde vives a que, si la realizaste en un lugar muy apartado, donde no hay un camino para llegar, donde no hay un transporte público para llegar.

Another reported use was metadata from research collection devices. The interview with Chile discussed the use of field survey metadata and its analysis to evaluate fieldwork performance. This also raised the question of whether such data qualifies as big data. Chilean respondents explained:

el mismo tema de los de los para datos que comentamos tiene una realidad, que no es la producción directa de un estimador o de un indicador, sino que más bien controlar que los relevamientos en terrenos se están realizando de forma correcta y con calidad y que no haya defraudaciones ni falseamientos

de instrumentos. Entonces en ese sentido, aporta, desde otro punto de vista a la producción del indicador, y eso digamos que por su volumen de datos es lo más parecido a big data que tenemos física. Se te ocurre otra cosa más. (Chile)

Bonaire, Brazil, Paraguay, Peru, and the Dominican Republic were the five countries that reported not using big data for other purposes.

Suppose the production of official statistics, experimental statistics, or studies using big data is not yet widespread. In that case, using big data for other purposes is unlikely to be more prevalent. This issue can be linked to mastering many skills, personnel, technological resources, and other requirements. Consequently, using big data for other purposes will naturally stem from its application in mapped statistical activities. Such use indicates mastery of necessary competencies, allowing the expansion of big data applications to additional purposes.

5.2.2. Resources needed to produce statistics

Informants from all 12 participating countries provided suggestions regarding the resources necessary for producing statistics with big data. Brazil and the Dominican Republic made the most suggestions, with six each, followed by Chile and Ecuador, with five each. However, identifying more or fewer suggestions depends on a categorization process that can be somewhat subjective, potentially oversimplifying the richness of the narratives. These accounts ranged from specific, practical needs to more general concerns addressing broader focus areas.

Even considering the inherent subjectivity in categorizing responses, common themes emerged that warrant attention. These themes align with recommendations in the United Nations Working Group on Big Data for Official Statistics Maturity Matrix (United Nations, 2020). This guide outlines four dimensions: Political and Legal Framework, IT Infrastructure, Human Resources, and Applications. These dimensions assess an institution's organizational maturity regarding big data work and provide a framework for organizing the challenges and weaknesses identified in the interviews.

Numerous suggestions for required resources were recorded, totaling 45 items distributed across at least five core themes. These themes closely align with the dimensions of the Maturity Matrix and cover data access, confidentiality, infrastructure, legislation, human resources, and applications.

The most frequently cited needs were related to IT infrastructure, mentioned by nine countries, and human resources, mentioned by ten countries.

References categorized under human resources included challenges such as retaining personnel within institutions competing with the private sector, providing ongoing training to keep up with new techniques and applications, and forming partnerships to enable production.

This issue was highlighted as a key challenge directly tied to institutions' ability to align statistical production priorities with their respective social contexts. Regional partnerships were seen as a means to continue production despite limited human resources, ensuring alignment with national interests.

Regarding human resources, what Chile stated:

Y agregaría también algo que es bien importante, que son las capacidades del funcionario. En nuestro equipo. Por fortuna, tenemos gente muy capacitada no tenemos problemas en ese sentido, pero no es así en todos los equipos. entonces yo creo que falta un poco de capacitación para que este conocimiento esté más distribuido y no esté como tan concentrado en un solo equipo o pocos equipos.

The interview with technicians from the Dominican Republic highlights the importance of human resource training:

Para continuar un poco ahí, comentarles que otra iniciativa voy a corroborar con la parte de la necesidad de capacitar más el personal en ese sentido, así como más recursos humanos.

In the same vein, the interview with Argentina brought similar statements:

A veces hay mucha rotación de personal. Entre lo que es el sector público y privado. Hay mucha competencia, entonces tenemos rotación en ciertos en ciertas posiciones, por ejemplo, en todas las posiciones relacionadas a informático.

Finally, it is important to report that the Argentine respondent explicitly mentioned the retention of human resources.

Principalmente contar con recursos humanos capacitados. Digamos, en la frontera de conocimiento del manejo de datos con las herramientas más eficientes. A veces hay mucha rotación de personal. Entre lo que es el sector público y privado. Hay mucha competencia, entonces tenemos rotación en ciertas posiciones, por ejemplo, en todas las posiciones relacionadas a informático.

Mexico, when addressing issues related to human resource needs, emphasizes the importance of partnerships:

Otra cosa que también es clave es la colaboración, la colaboración con instituciones privadas, con instituciones gubernamentales, con otras oficinas de estadística. Esta parte de los HUBs regionales, también de los grupos de la

ONU, es clave no poder tener esa colaboración, Estar abiertos a la colaboración también es algo necesario para poder.

Infrastructure-related needs were among the most frequently mentioned, encompassing issues related to data processing and storage and, to a lesser extent, access to suitable applications. References to data processing and storage were generally associated with the need for modern and powerful equipment.

Interviewees from Colombia highlighted this point:

Uy, pues esa pregunta es compleja porque inicialmente, pues por la experiencia que yo he tenido, lo primero que se necesita es la capacidad tecnológica, o sea, si nosotros no tenemos o no compramos espacio en la nube servidores en la nube para manejar volúmenes muy grandes de información. y tampoco tenemos dentro del Danne equipos que tengan la capacidad de procesar y visualizar esa información. Es muy difícil.

Paraguay highlights the importance of having a comprehensive infrastructure, not only in terms of equipment but also regarding software licenses:

Y ahí es todo un tema de infraestructura, Leo, que hay que tener preparado detrás. A veces implica pagos de licencias, pagos de infraestructura que tiene un costo, y queremos ser bien las cosas. Y muchas veces te dice, no hay presupuesto y tenés que tratar de ver con lo que tenés y no alcanza. Yo no sé si todas partes, pero eso es un tema también.

Data access and legal frameworks are closely linked categories. Respondents noted difficulties engaging with private companies to obtain relevant data for planning and training human resources. On the other hand, outdated or non-existent legal frameworks hinder access to big data. Five of the 12 countries—Argentina, Brazil, Chile, Mexico, and the Dominican Republic—expressed concerns in these areas.

Argentina emphasized the limitations of its legal framework, citing legislation from 1968 that predates the concept of big data. Brazil approached the issue from an institutional strengthening perspective, addressing interconnected challenges related to human resources and infrastructure:

Bom primeiro recurso é ter acesso, né? Tem um empoderamento institucional maior, uma estrutura ágil pra conseguir o acesso as informações. E para um Big Data, que você vai precisar de um volume grande de dados pra armazenar e processar, etc., você vai precisar de uma infraestrutura de TI robusta. E você precisa de pessoas com habilidades pra lidar com essas informações, pra construir essa estrutura, e também em diferentes níveis de expertise, né? Pra construir estrutura, outro que vai analisar e desenvolver os modelos. Enfim, se for necessário, precisa de mais estrutura. Nesse sentido mais pessoal e mais investimento em infraestrutura de TI. (Brasil)

The volume of suggestions and the wealth of details provided could result in many citations, which this report cannot accommodate. Therefore, we recommend reviewing the summarized response sheets from the countries to illustrate this diversity. What can be

emphasized as a synthesis of the need for producing statistics with big data is the sensitivity to each country's “key” factors in adopting this type of data for national statistical production.

There are clear and systematic indications of the need for human resources, not only in terms of different specializations but also in their ongoing training and capacity building, as well as policies for retaining such personnel in competition with private entities. These elements are repeatedly highlighted in the interviews, as is the need for access to technological infrastructure resources, given the unique nature of this type of data, encompassing processing capacity, storage, and, further upstream, access to the data itself.

5.2.3. Expertise or resources to share

Informants from seven countries provided 17 indications of experiences or resources to share. The most commonly mentioned experiences included natural language processing, data anonymization, training offerings for using alternative data sources, applications of satellite imagery, economic nowcasting indicators, and data visualization.

Sharing experiences requires the knowledge to conduct an action or activity and the capacity for documentation, systematization, and the creation of resources that others can use. Depending on the type of practice or expertise, sharing may demand varying efforts from the institution involved.

Regarding expertise in natural language processing, Brazil, Colombia, and Mexico reported having experience. Additionally, Colombia indicated it has already shared its work with other countries, specifically Kenya and Ghana.

Ahí también tenemos algunos, un par de proyectos que han venido trabajando, que hemos desde el año pasado, que también podríamos compartir que, de hecho, estuvimos en un acuerdo de cooperación con Kenia y con Gana para dar a conocer esa experiencia de Colombia. E bueno, lo que mencionó todo lo de procesamiento, lenguaje natural. También lo podríamos compartir (Colombia)

Em relação ao uso de imagens de satélites, as experiências estão relacionadas com a disponibilização de repositórios públicos como Github⁹ e Gitlab¹⁰ pelo Chile. O México

⁹ Github is a cloud based open-source platform software collaborative work and version control that allows simultaneous work on the same content.

¹⁰ Gitlab is a cloud based open-source platform that helps management of software development.

apontou possuir inúmeras parcerias, inclusive com INE do Chile, Belize e República Dominicana. A iniciativa mais ampla citada é de projeto de colaboração para montagem de laboratório de análise de dados geoespaciais, com a Universidade das Índias Ocidentais (The University of West Indies) e a Comunidade dos Estados Latino-Americanos e Caribenhos (CELAC), para criar uma plataforma regional de análise de imagens de satélites, assim como com o Hub Regional para Big Data no Brasil.

Ainda em alusão ao uso de imagens de satélite, o depoimento do México é importante pois menciona um trabalho estruturado e sólido em diferentes frentes:

Sí de hecho, pues, digo, hemos participado en distintos foros donde hemos compartido estas experiencias. Actualmente tenemos ya proyectos de colaboración muy, muy específicos con el línea de Chile. Tenemos un proyecto de colaboración que estamos en el primer año, pero sigue para el siguiente año, donde estamos de alguna manera transfiriendo nuestra flujo tecnológico para poder aprovechar big data. Ellos ya lo están incorporando en su en su en el instituto, están haciendo. Más y de este tipo de tecnología. También con este, con el Caribe tenemos un proyecto también de colaboración muy importante en donde les ayudamos a montar su laboratorio geoespacial con la con la Universidad de West Indies. Pero esta infraestructura está prevista para que lo aproveche toda la región del Caribe. Para hacer todo esto, todos estos productos de análisis espacial experimental con imágenes satelitales.

Brazil and Ecuador have privacy-preserving techniques for data anonymization. This topic is a key topic in all discussions about access to big data but was rarely mentioned during the interviews. This highlights the importance of mentioning it as an area of expertise to be shared.

Brazil reports having resources for training in price index calculation, which it has conducted through courses on web scraping, as well as in natural language processing and data anonymization. Regarding the latter, the Brazilian informant stated:

Acho que tem pessoas que têm avançado em áreas como processamento de linguagens naturais. Então também já teve colega que teve interação com o instituto na região, em projetos nisso. Tem também iniciativas na área de técnicas de, como é que chama? Em português, eles deram uma tradução, mas é de melhoria de privacidade ou não sei se exatamente o termo é esse, mas é uma maneira de você tentar compartilhar os seus dados de maneira mais segura, né? Colegas trabalhando nesse sentido, e também colaborando com o INES da região (Brasil)

Regarding the production of price indices through courses:

A gente ministrou dois cursos no ramo. Então não foi sobre o webscraping pra índices de preço. Teve um seminário de três dias com três sessões sobre isso, e o outro foi sobre processamento. Principais etapas pra tratar dados de fontes alternativas pra índices de preço e cálculo de índices pra diferentes metodologias. Então isso foi algo que a gente já fez.

Other resources mentioned include data anonymization, for which Brazil and Ecuador have expertise; Uruguay's handling of mobile phone data; and Ecuador's citation of data visualization techniques.

Ecuador also presents an interesting approach to overcoming the lack of robust computational resources by using an algorithm that distributes processing across a computer cluster called Hadoop.

The Dominican Republic highlighted its significant experience mapping the phenomenon of sargassum and noted partnerships already established with other Caribbean countries, such as Cuba and Mexico. These accounts illustrate how local contexts can catalyze partnerships, as shared experiences provide opportunities to bring countries and their institutions closer together, fostering the exchange of solutions, work techniques, and experiences.

Caso de lo del sargazo verdadero, la medición del Sargazo, que es un tema que no sé si ustedes verdad saben que toda la cuenca del Caribe, de alguna manera tenemos incidencias sobre este este fenómeno. Puede algo que estamos igual que compartiendo. Lo hemos hecho con otras instituciones. En el caso del Instituto de Estadísticas de la Oficina Nacional Estadística de Cuba. Estuvo con nosotros compartiendo información, está ahí disponible. Yo creo que ha sido una experiencia interesante, sobre todo en el caso del Caribe. que hay bastantes disponibilidades institucionales en los institutos nacionales estadísticas, pues creo que una experiencia interesante esta buena disposición y podemos compartir. No sé Paola, Si tú corroboras o creerías que otro tema. Sí también. Por ejemplo, así como mencionaba Miosotis, el caso de las estadísticas experimentales partir de sobre sargazo nos formó una coyuntura también para este intercambio de experiencia, sobre todo con el Instituto con el Inegi de México. Entonces, para conversarles sobre las experiencias que nosotros tuvimos utilizando fuentes no tradicionales para captar sargazo, básicamente porque México es uno de los países que más impacto negativo ha recibido por el por este fenómeno. Entonces ellos tienen experiencia en término tanto de planificación y captación de estas estadísticas. (Dominican Republic)

The presentation of expertise to share does not merely reflect what countries have already developed. It also stems from other factors, such as establishing partnerships between national statistical institutes and their technical staff, documenting such experiences, and sharing similar contexts or priorities that foster mutual interest.

5.3. Notes on the in-depth interviews

In-depth interviews are moments where individuals exchange experiences, share impressions, and provide information on one or more questions or topics outlined in a script, which was the case in this study.

The interviewee or group of interviewees might have varying levels of information on the subject. Measures were taken to ensure participants were more aligned with the topic, such as sending invitations highlighting the theme or providing scheduling details accompanied by clarifications about how the in-depth interview would proceed.

Nevertheless, specific situations arose in each interview, which we documented for sharing. It is important to note that these are not personal evaluations of the informants but reflections on the work dynamics and their effectiveness in achieving the intended results.

Argentina had only one interviewee. Overall, the impression was that there was limited investment in the topic, and the interviewee appeared uncomfortable with the questions, possibly due to a lack of experience or information to report.

For Bonaire, the interview was conducted in English, but the audio had significant noise, as though someone was speaking in a tunnel. Efforts were made to improve the sound quality, but at times, communication was unintelligible due to audio issues and because English was not the interviewees' native language. Additionally, the respondents from Bonaire often played a secondary role, with the representatives from the Netherlands taking the lead in responses. Interestingly, one participant was in Bonaire while the other was in the Netherlands. The interview revealed that Bonaire lacks local personnel or computational resources to work with big data, as the Netherlands' statistics institute manages these tasks. This highlighted the need for local personnel with sensitivity and perception to determine what is relevant for big data production and an understanding of the local context.

The interview with Brazil reflected characteristics observed in others, particularly that the respondent had only partial knowledge of the institution's initiatives. Various experiences, particularly with web scraping, were noted for producing official, experimental statistics and studies.

The interview with Chile saw the last-minute participation of additional technical staff, which the team immediately identified as a positive development. SDG 11 is featured in their plans for 2024. An interesting aspect was the mention of cooperation with Mexico, though this collaboration was not referenced in Mexico's own interview.

Colombia's interview focused on statistics for violence indicators related to peace agreements. Communication challenges arose due to audio and connection issues. Colombia reported cooperation agreements with Kenya and Ghana on natural language processing.

The interview with Ecuador faced difficulties due to the respondent's rapid speaking pace, which complicated information capture even with recordings. This challenge was

communicated during the interview, leading to a change in the meeting platform and the inclusion of colleagues via the same connection to facilitate better communication.

Responses from Guatemala consistently indicated minimal engagement with big data, and the in-depth interview offered little additional insight beyond prior consultation responses. Notably, the interviewee equated big data with national statistics, prompting the team to clarify their broader understanding of its relationship with national and regional statistics. Similar connection issues were encountered with Ecuador.

In Mexico, big data is not used to produce official statistics but is employed for experimental statistics and studies. The respondent demonstrated a strong understanding of big data, aligned with the interview's framework. They highlighted three public satellite image products routinely updated for monitoring vegetation cover, agricultural production, water bodies, and human settlements. Mexico's interview stood out for its wealth of examples across various questions.

For Paraguay, big data was associated with integrating extensive datasets from diverse sources, such as implementing a national identity registry. Multidimensional poverty studies involved big data, though specific datasets were not detailed. The respondent also mentioned an agreement with Korea but could not specify which Korea.

Peru's interviewees began by discussing big data's conceptualization, emphasizing volume and variety while downplaying velocity. Key projects included poverty mapping using administrative data and mobile data usage during the pandemic for citizen engagement. Communication difficulties arose because participants were seated far from the microphone, which persisted despite feedback. At one point, a senior team member acknowledged the team's limited experience, creating tension and necessitating clarification of the interview's purpose and expectations.

The Dominican Republic provided limited information, as anticipated from prior consultation responses. Despite few experiences, they identified environmental statistics as a potential focus, sharing experiences on sargassum monitoring with countries like Mexico and Cuba.

In Uruguay, the interview began by discussing big data concepts to provide accurate responses. The respondent highlighted work with mobile data and supermarket data for price indices. Mobile data usage involved indirect access, with telecommunications companies producing aggregated data for the statistics institute.

The in-depth interviews provided access to a wide range of information and proved an excellent tool for capturing practices more precisely than online surveys. Their manageable

duration likely encouraged participation, which may not have been as successful with more extended interviews. However, limitations arose, such as informants lacking direct expertise in big data or larger teams potentially providing incomplete responses.

Using responses from prior consultations to guide interviews proved helpful in aligning answers more closely with reality. However, this approach did not eliminate disorganized responses, as interviewees sometimes provided answers unrelated to the specific questions despite being familiar with the script.

6. Findings

The survey concludes that work involving big data for official statistics showed the most minor combinations of Big Data Types and Topics. The number of indications progressively increased when moving to experimental statistics, studies, and plans.

Belize, Grenada, and Guatemala responded negatively to almost all structuring questions. Therefore, out of the 15 countries that responded to the survey, the adequate number of respondents representing the total is 12, except for the question about plans, which Belize answered.

The most frequently marked combinations in the matrix were Population as a Topic with Satellite Imagery (7 indications) and Mobile Phone Data (6 indications) in the questions regarding studies and plans. Another frequently indicated Topic was Prices combined with Web Scraping. This combination received five indications in the questions about studies and plans and four about official and experimental statistics. These last two cases represented the most total indications for such questions.

Individually, Population and Prices were the most common Topics for statistics across all four structuring questions and, thus, for the group of countries. Regarding big data types, satellite imagery, and web scraping were the most frequently mentioned in all structuring questions.

The survey results indicate the prominence of using more common types of big data, particularly Satellite Imagery and Web Scraping. From the perspective of in-depth interviews, the most common Big Data Types aligned with those identified in the survey.

On the other hand, there was a discrepancy in the responses regarding official statistics between the two research instruments. The standardization of understanding of the concept of big data explains this difference. The interviewing team observed this weakness during the interviews.

While the interview script included concepts such as official and experimental statistics and examples of using big data for other purposes, the idea of big data itself was not part of the explanations or clarifications.

The survey responses were declarative and lacked supporting evidence. Any differences in understanding the concepts or questions may produce results that do not fully align with reality. The in-depth interviews yielded more reliable results, as they involved more personal contact, clarifying doubts about the questions being asked.

For some countries, using large amounts of data derived from integrating different datasets from various institutions was freely identified as an exercise in big data. This logic made sense to the interviewees for several reasons:

- Regarding Variety: The challenge of integrating a set of structured records from different institutions into a single database, initiated at various times and with diverse levels of complexity. In other words, for all practical purposes, this meets the classification criterion of big data concerning varied or unstructured data, as the challenge of integration requires the creation of a new structure to enable its use.
- Regarding Volume: This structuring process confronts the individuals involved with a large amount of data, which was another reason cited for identifying the work as involving big data. It is not a matter of making value judgments about the quantity; instead, it is essential to recognize that, on the scale of the institution, the technical capacity of staff or equipment to complete the task cannot be overlooked. This may justify this perception.

The responses on producing official statistics using big data reveal a process of structuring institutional frameworks, resources, and practices that require administrative data.

In the survey, the most recurring Topics were Population-related statistics, followed by Prices. Open-ended responses provided additional contributions, though not all could be fully utilized due to the need for critical adjustments to align them with the question's objective, resulting in some being excluded.

The approach for reaching respondents was to avoid interviewing individuals unfamiliar with or without relevant information on the subject. A different approach might have yielded fewer qualified informants. The chosen communication flow proved most effective in establishing solid institutional relationships for developing the work.

During interviews, reviewing responses from previous consultations or providing examples of elements in the question often facilitated the generation of relevant responses, either by clarifying the question or prompting recollection of similar work.

However, it is noteworthy that the interviewee was not always from a department working with big data or related fields. This became evident when the need arose to consult colleagues more directly involved in significant data initiatives.

Despite challenges related to using big data, cost was rarely mentioned. This is explained by a preference for using Web Scraping and public Satellite Imagery instead of paid data sources, for which interviewees indicated a lack of resources. This scarcity of funding was especially notable given the frequent mention of fragile infrastructure. Paid external data acquisition, such as data from X (formerly Twitter) or mobile phone data, was only sporadically referenced.

Working with big data presents organizations with new challenges, particularly concerning privacy and data protection and the need for skilled human resources. These themes recurred during the in-depth interviews.

Regarding privacy, some respondents reported receiving company inquiries about how privacy and competitiveness concerns would be addressed. Companies feared losing customer trust or competitive advantage, highlighting the real significance of privacy concerns.

From a methodological standpoint, working with big data fundamentally differs from traditional statistics. The target population is defined in the latter, followed by sampling and instrument preparation. With big data, however, access to data often precedes defining the studied population. This shift introduces challenges in using traditional methods for processing and analysis, given the much more significant, unstructured data volumes requiring greater computational capacity. Adopting and developing new ways is an unavoidable challenge. Some challenges were recruiting qualified personnel, adopting new software, paying for licenses, training staff, and retaining them despite competitive market salaries.

Although literature exists on big data and Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), the interviews did not reveal significant connections between the two topics, indicating that most countries do not relate their work with big data to SDGs.

7. Recommendations

The recommendations address the challenges posed by implementing big data in national statistical institutes (NSIs), drawing from elements of the United Nations Maturity Matrix (2020). Recommendations are organized into the following categories:

- Legal Challenges
- Ethical Challenges

- Technical Challenges
- Technological Challenges
- Operational Challenges

Legal Challenges: The legal dimension is of utmost importance and, as highlighted in the literature, is closely associated with access, privacy, and confidentiality of big data. However, the interviews did not emphasize this issue. When legal aspects were mentioned, they were not directly associated with other concerns but rather with outdated legislation that inadequately facilitates data access. Big data is commonly linked to data from social networks, mobile phone usage records, banking, or web navigation data, often suggesting involvement with global companies. However, this is not always accurate, as it can also involve national public or private institutions, including other governmental sectors.

Legal challenges begin with updating national legislation to address privacy and confidentiality, which is often straightforward for traditional data production methods by national statistical institutes (NSIs) but does not cover new data production approaches.

Accessing national legislation to study or compare legal frameworks is not always straightforward. However, a quick online search can uncover European legislation on the topic. Companies offering web services, connectivity, storage, or cloud processing often present the legal frameworks of the countries they operate in on their websites.

Based on the interviews, addressing legal challenges effectively requires a simultaneous focus on national and regional dimensions. Nationally, legislation must adapt to a world where public and private, national and international institutions collaborate on big data access to meet state decision-making needs while respecting individual rights, freedoms, and privacy.

Internationally, there is a pressing need for agreements to establish legal frameworks that protect countries and their populations from the private appropriation of personal data. This is especially important for countries with limited bargaining power against global companies.

Legal challenges often serve as the first barrier to data access. As noted by the United Nations (2014): "While most respondents recognize the challenges related to IT, skills, legislation, and methodology, most argue that the biggest challenge for most Big Data projects is the limited access to potential datasets."

Ethical Challenges: Accessing data immediately raises concerns about its use—questions such as what data can be accessed, by whom, and under what conditions naturally arise. Big data is no exception. Unlike traditional data production, where NSIs produce and store data themselves, big data production and storage often involve third parties. Citizens voluntarily generate the data, but third parties store it. NSIs operate within established legal frameworks and must adhere to them, whereas private companies often rely on implicit user consent. Privacy and ethical standards in data usage also vary across cultures, complicating the establishment of universal norms.

Ethical challenges go hand in hand with legal challenges and must be addressed accordingly. Establishing national commissions responsible for data protection is imperative to safeguard citizens and, by extension, national states, as exemplified by the European Union's General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR).

NSIs are legally accountable and systematically work to maintain public trust and acceptance. Their data impacts public policy decisions, subjecting them to ongoing public scrutiny and judgment.

While private companies do not bear direct responsibilities for public policies, they operate within national legal frameworks and must adhere to them, just as citizens do. Engaging in any stage of big data handling, regardless of how the data is produced, does not exempt stakeholders from following standards of ethics, privacy, and confidentiality. The critical question is defining these standards.

Technical Challenges: Big data presents numerous technical challenges. In-depth interviews highlighted that NSI professionals in Latin America and the Caribbean are aware of these challenges and are actively addressing them.

The work program for the UN Regional Hub for Big Data in Brazil (September 2023–August 2024) outlines a key objective: "Strengthening ties and promoting cooperation among official statistics producers in the region." Specifically, it aims to support "knowledge sharing and collaboration among producers and users, enhancing the utilization of generated knowledge."

The Hub facilitates various training activities for professionals interested in the subject. Content is presented chronologically, with the corresponding language indicated. Appendix E provides a complete list of these resources.

Regarding the actions of the Hub in Brazil, those focused on capacity building include the promotion of numerous webinars as part of the sharing of work experiences among

countries. This can be observed on the video page, which features more than 15 webinars in Spanish, English, and Portuguese, covering the period from December 2021 to October 2024. Accessing available technical knowledge is one of the steps to be taken. Additionally, there is a UN Course Catalog on the topic, offering training content through learning paths—a concept widely used in distance education that allows for the selection of content and materials tailored to the learner's personal interests. One of the documents available in the catalog is the Competency Framework for Big Data Acquisition and Processing, which enables the alignment of training needs with available courses by identifying competency gaps.

Strengthening trust networks, such as the Regional Hub, and expanding partnerships among NSIs in Latin America and the Caribbean are essential. Shared contexts enable a better exchange of experiences, as these countries' institutional agendas tend to align closely.

Technological Challenges: Technological challenges are more evident than others and highlight financial constraints on NSIs' development and the need for innovative solutions. The United Nations has established working groups to address issues related to big data use, providing valuable tools and resources.

Task Teams focus on specific topics and are valuable for addressing technological challenges. The UN's Global Platform operates under four pillars:

- Trusted Partners
- Trusted Data
- Trusted Methods
- Trusted Learning

The interviews revealed many references to technological problems and the solutions implemented, or in some cases, the interruption of work. Big data requires technologies distinct from those used in traditional statistics. It is not merely a matter of more extensive data volumes but of fundamentally different data characterized by high velocity, variety, and volume.

Operational Challenges: Operational challenges primarily relate to using big data and the issues it poses for NSIs. A distinctive feature of this work is the trust these institutions must maintain as they produce data, indicators, or analyses for public use and policymaking.

Addressing these challenges involves ensuring qualified human resources, training these professionals, and continuously updating their knowledge of methods and technologies. Retaining skilled personnel, given competitive market salaries, is another significant challenge.

Institutionally, even when resource-related challenges are mitigated, others arise from the relationships between institutions, their independence, or subordination within national statistical systems. Legal responsibilities for information dissemination intersect with public opinion, dissemination platforms, and the credibility of institutions, which are relational and influenced by the data released.

Methodological Challenges: Today's methods for working with big data may not apply tomorrow. What constitutes big data today may be discontinued or replaced by new data types arising from emerging resources, services, or public and market demands.

New types of big data may require new acquisition, analysis, or visualization methods. Current or new techniques and applications can facilitate work with existing and emerging big data. The challenge lies in equipping teams with the skills and experience to adapt and integrate these methods into workflows.

Functioning teams are the minimum requirement for developing or critically evaluating new methods. This capacity ensures data processing aligns with local priorities, whether for big data or traditional data.

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Appendix

Appendix A – Online questionnaire

Consulta Internacional sobre el uso de Big Data para Estadísticas en América Latina y el Caribe **International Consultation on the use of Big Data for Statistics in Latin America and the Caribbean** Consulta Internacional sobre o uso de Big Data para Estatísticas na América Latina e Caribe

* Indica uma pergunta obrigatória

1. E-mail *

2. Idioma/Language *

Marcar apenas uma oval.

Español

English *Pular para a pergunta 26*

Português *Pular para a pergunta 49*

BIENVENIDA, BIENVENIDO!

El Hub Regional de Big Data de las Naciones Unidas te invita a participar en la Consulta Internacional sobre el uso de Big Data para Estadísticas OFICIALES y EXPERIMENTALES en América Latina y el Caribe. Su respuesta ayudará a brindar una visión general del uso de big data en la producción estadística por parte de los Institutos Nacionales de Estadística de la región y puede ayudar a orientar la asignación de recursos para respaldar esta práctica.

Tiempo de respuesta estimado: 15 min.

3. País *

4. Organización *

5. Nombre

USO DE BIG DATA PARA LAS ESTADÍSTICAS OFICIALES

6. ¿El Instituto de Estadística utiliza big data para estadísticas oficiales? *

Marcar apenas uma oval.

Sí

No *Pular para a pergunta 10*

TIPOS DE BIG DATA Y TEMAS

7. Seleccione todas las que correspondan *

Marque todas que se aplican.

	Precios	Población	Agricultura	Medio ambiente	Ninguno de esos
Raspado Web	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Imágenes satelitales	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Telefonía móvil	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Dados escaneados	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Medidores de consumo	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Transacciones financieras	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Sensores de carretera	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Seguimiento de barcos	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Medidores de salud	<input type="checkbox"/>				

8. ¿El Instituto de Estadística utiliza alguna otra combinación de tipo de big data y tema? *

Marcar apenas una oval.

Sí

No *Pular para a pergunta 10*

9. Que tipo de big data y tema? (Solo si respondiste sí a la pregunta anterior)

USO DE BIG DATA PARA LAS ESTADÍSTICAS EXPERIMENTALES

10. ¿El Instituto de Estadística utiliza big data para estadísticas experimentales? *

Marcar apenas una oval.

Sí

No *Pular para a pergunta 14*

TIPOS DE BIG DATA Y TEMAS

11. Seleccione todas las que correspondan *

Marque todas que se aplican.

	Precios	Población	Agricultura	Medio ambiente	Ninguno de esos
Raspado Web	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Imágenes satelitales	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Telefonía móvil	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Dados escaneados	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Medidores de consumo	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Transacciones financieras	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Sensores de carretera	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Seguimiento de barcos	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Medidores de salud	<input type="checkbox"/>				

12. ¿El Instituto de Estadística utiliza alguna otra combinación de tipo de big data y tema? *

Marcar apenas una oval.

Sí

No *Pular para a pergunta 14*

13. Que tipo de big data y tema? (Solo si respondiste sí a la pregunta anterior)

REALIZACIÓN DE ESTUDIOS O PRUEBAS

14. ¿El Instituto de Estadística estudia el uso de big data para estadística? *

Marcar apenas una oval.

Sí

No *Pular para a pergunta 18*

TIPOS DE BIG DATA Y TEMAS

15. Seleccione todas las que correspondan *

Marque todas que se aplican.

	Precios	Población	Agricultura	Medio ambiente	Ninguno de esos
Raspado Web	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Imágenes satelitales	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Telefonía móvil	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Dados escaneados	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Medidores de consumo	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Transacciones financieras	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Sensores de carretera	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Seguimiento de barcos	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Medidores de salud	<input type="checkbox"/>				

16. ¿El Instituto de Estadística estudia alguna otra combinación de tipo de big data y tema? *

Marcar apenas una oval.

Sí

No *Pular para a pergunta 18*

17. Que tipo de big data y tema? (Solo si respondiste sí a la pregunta anterior)

PLANES PARA EL FUTURO

18. ¿Tiene previsto el instituto de estadística iniciar nuevos usos del big data? *

Marcar apenas una oval.

Sí

No *Pular para a pergunta 22*

TIPOS DE BIG DATA Y TEMAS

19. Seleccione todas las que correspondan *

Marque todas que se aplican.

	Precios	Población	Agricultura	Medio ambiente	Ninguno de esos
Raspado Web	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Imágenes satelitales	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Telefonía móvil	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Dados escaneados	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Medidores de consumo	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Transacciones financieras	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Sensores de carretera	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Seguimiento de barcos	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Medidores de salud	<input type="checkbox"/>				

20. ¿El Instituto de Estadística planea utilizar alguna otra combinación de tipo de big data y tema? *

Marcar apenas una oval.

Sí

No *Pular para a pergunta 22*

21. Que tipo de big data y tema? (Solo si respondiste sí a la pregunta anterior)

RECURSOS Y NECESIDADES REGIONALES

22. ¿Tiene el Instituto de Estadística algún recurso o experiencia en el uso de big data que pueda ser compartido con otros países? Si es así, ¿cuáles?

23. ¿Cuáles son las limitaciones y necesidades para el uso de big data en la producción estadística en su país?

24. Indique los temas de capacitación de mayor interés o necesidad inmediata.

25. ¿Existen otras contribuciones que puedan ayudar al Hub a planificar acciones para apoyar el uso de big data en la Región?

WELCOME!

The United Nations Regional Hub for Big Data invites you to participate in the International Consultation on the use of Big Data for OFFICIAL and EXPERIMENTAL Statistics in Latin America and the Caribbean. Your response will help to provide an overview of the use of big data in statistical production by the National Statistical Institutes in the region and may help guide the allocation of resources to support this practice.
Estimated response time: 15 min.

26. Country *

27. Institute *

28. Name

USE OF BIG DATA FOR OFFICIAL STATISTICS

29. Does the National Statical Office use big data for official statistics? *

Marcar apenas uma oval.

Yes

No *Pular para a pergunta 33*

BIG DATA TYPES AND TOPICS

30. Select all that apply *

Marque todas que se aplicam.

	Prices	Population	Agriculture	Environment	None of those
Web scraping	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Satellite imagery	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Mobile phone data	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Scanner data	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Smart meter	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Financial transactions	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Road sensors	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Ship identification	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Health records	<input type="checkbox"/>				

31. Does the National Statical Office use any other combination of big data type and topic? *

Marcar apenas uma oval.

Yes

No *Pular para a pergunta 33*

32. What type of big data and topic? (Only if you answered yes to the previous question)

USE OF BIG DATA FOR EXPERIMENTAL STATISTICS

33. Does the National Statical Office use big data for experimental statistics? *

Marcar apenas uma oval.

Yes

No *Pular para a pergunta 37*

BIG DATA TYPES AND TOPICS

34. Select all that apply *

Marque todas que se aplicam.

	Prices	Population	Agriculture	Environment	None of those
Web scraping	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Satellite imagery	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Mobile phone data	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Scanner data	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Smart meter	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Financial transactions	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Road sensors	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Ship identification	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Health records	<input type="checkbox"/>				

35. Does the National Statistical Office use any other combination of big data type and topic? *

Marcar apenas uma oval. Yes No *Pular para a pergunta 37*

36. What type of big data and topic? (Only if you answered yes to the previous question)

CONDUCTING STUDIES OR TESTS

37. Does the National Statistical Office study the use of big data for statistics? *

Marcar apenas uma oval. Yes No *Pular para a pergunta 41*

BIG DATA TYPES AND TOPICS

38. Select all that apply *

Marque todas que se aplicam.

	Prices	Population	Agriculture	Environment	None of those
Web scraping	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Satellite imagery	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Mobile phone data	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Scanner data	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Smart meter	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Financial transactions	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Road sensors	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Ship identification	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Health records	<input type="checkbox"/>				

39. Does the National Statical Office study any other combination of big data type and topic? *

Marcar apenas uma oval.

Yes

No *Pular para a pergunta 41*

40. What type of big data and topic? (Only if you answered yes to the previous question)

PLANS FOR THE FUTURE

41. Does the National Statical Office plan to initiate new uses of big data? *

Marcar apenas uma oval.

Yes

No *Pular para a pergunta 45*

BIG DATA TYPES AND TOPICS

42. Select all that apply *

Marque todas que se aplicam.

	Prices	Population	Agriculture	Environment	None of those
Web scraping	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Satellite imagery	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Mobile phone data	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Scanner data	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Smart meter	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Financial transactions	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Road sensors	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Ship identification	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Health records	<input type="checkbox"/>				

43. Does the National Statistical Office plan to use any other combination of big data type and topic? *

Marcar apenas uma oval. Yes No *Pular para a pergunta 45*

44. What type of big data and topic? (Only if you answered yes to the previous question)

REGIONAL RESOURCES AND NEEDS

45. Does the Statistical Office have any resource or expertise in the use of big data that might be shared with other countries? If any, which?

46. What are the limitations and needs for the use of big data in statistical production in your country?

47. Indicate the training topics of greatest interest or immediate need.

48. Exist any further contributions that would help the Hub in organizing its plans for supporting the use of big data in the region?

BEM-VINDA, BEM-VINDO!

O Hub Regional das Nações Unidas para Big Data convida a participar da Consulta Internacional sobre o uso de Big Data para Estatísticas OFICIAIS e EXPERIMENTAIS na América Latina e Caribe. Sua resposta ajudará a traçar um panorama do uso de big data na produção estatística pelos Institutos Nacionais de Estatística da região e poderá ajudar a orientar a alocação de recursos para o apoio a essa prática.

Tempo de resposta estimado: 15 min.

49. País *

50. Instituição

51. Nome *

BIG DATA PARA ESTATÍSTICAS OFICIAIS

52. O Instituto de Estatística usa big data para estatísticas oficiais? *

Marcar apenas uma oval.

Sim

Não *Pular para a pergunta 56*

TIPOS DE BIG DATA E TÓPICOS

53. Selecione todas as opções aplicáveis *

Marque todas que se aplicam.

	Preços	População	Agricultura	Meio ambiente	Nenhum desses
Raspagem da web	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Imagens de satélite	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Dados de telefonia móvel	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Dados de scanner	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Medidores de consumo	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Transações financeiras	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Sensores rodoviários	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Sensores de navios	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Medidores de saúde	<input type="checkbox"/>				

54. O Instituto de Estatística usa alguma outra combinação de tipo de big data e tópico? *

Marcar apenas uma oval.

Sim

Não *Pular para a pergunta 56*

55. Que tipo de big data e tópico? (Somente se respondeu sim na pergunta anterior)

USO DE BIG DATA PARA ESTATÍSTICAS EXPERIMENTAIS

56. O Instituto de Estatística usa big data para estatísticas experimentais? *

Marcar apenas uma oval.

Sim

Não *Pular para a pergunta 60*

TIPOS DE BIG DATA E TÓPICOS

57. Selecione todas as opções aplicáveis *

Marque todas que se aplicam.

	Preços	População	Agricultura	Meio ambiente	Nenhum desses
Raspagem da web	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Imagens de satélite	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Dados de telefonia móvel	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Dados de scanner	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Medidores de consumo	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Transações financeiras	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Sensores rodoviários	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Sensores de navio	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Medidores de saúde	<input type="checkbox"/>				

58. O Instituto de Estatística usa alguma outra combinação de tipo de big data e tópico? *

Marcar apenas uma oval.

Sim

Não *Pular para a pergunta 60*

59. Que tipo de big data e tópico? (Somente se respondeu sim na pergunta anterior)

ESTUDOS OU TESTES

60. O Instituto de Estatística estuda o uso de big data para estatísticas? *

Marcar apenas uma oval.

Sim

Não *Pular para a pergunta 64*

TIPOS DE BIG DATA E TÓPICOS

61. Selecione todas as opções aplicáveis *

Marque todas que se aplicam.

	Preços	População	Agricultura	Meio ambiente	Nenhum desses
Raspagem da web	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Imagens de satélite	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Dados de telefonia móvel	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Dados de scanner	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Medidores de consumo	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Transações financeiras	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Sensores rodoviários	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Sensores de navio	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Medidores de saúde	<input type="checkbox"/>				

62. O Instituto de Estatística usa alguma outra combinação de tipo de big data e tópico? *

Marcar apenas uma oval. Sim Não *Pular para a pergunta 64*

63. Que tipo de big data e tópico? (Somente se respondeu sim na pergunta anterior)

PLANOS PARA O FUTURO

64. O Instituto de Estatística planeja iniciar novos usos de big data? *

Marcar apenas uma oval. Sim Não *Pular para a pergunta 68*

TIPOS DE BIG DATA E TÓPICOS

65. Selecione todas as opções aplicáveis *

Marque todas que se aplicam.

	Preços	População	Agricultura	Meio ambiente	Nenhum desses
Raspagem da web	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Imagens de satélite	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Dados de telefonia móvel	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Dados de scanner	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Medidores de consumo	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Transações financeiras	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Sensores rodoviários	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Sensores de navio	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Medidores de saúde	<input type="checkbox"/>				

66. O Instituto de Estatística usa alguma outra combinação de tipo de big data e tópico? *

Marcar apenas uma oval. Sim Não *Pular para a pergunta 68*

67. Que tipo de big data e tópico? (Somente se respondeu sim na pergunta anterior)

RECURSOS E NECESSIDADES REGIONAIS

68. O Instituto de Estatística possui algum recurso ou expertise no uso de big data que possa ser compartilhado com outros países? Se sim, quais?

69. Quais são as limitações e necessidades para o uso de big data na produção estatística em seu país?

70. Indique os tópicos de capacitação de maior interesse ou necessidade imediata.

71. Há alguma outra contribuição que possa ajudar o Hub a planejar ações para apoiar o uso de big data na região?

Este conteúdo não foi criado nem aprovado pelo Google.

Google Formulários

Appendix B – Script for in-depth interviews

International Consultation on the Use of Big Data in Latin America and the Caribbean

Script for In-Depth Interview

Date/Time:

Country:

Institution:

Interviewee:

BEGINNING

Hello, thank you very much for agreeing to participate in this interview!

My name is Leonardo Mello, and together with Hanna Cunha, we are responsible for conducting the in-depth interviews for the International Consultation on the Use of Big Data in Latin America and the Caribbean, developed by the UN Regional Hub for Big Data, with the support of the United Nations Population Fund (UNFPA).

Today, we will discuss the use of big data in the production of official and experimental statistics in your statistical institute/office. Our conversation will last approximately 60 minutes.

The information provided will be used to prepare a publication that will include the results of consultations conducted in 2022, 2023, and 2024. We hope this will help better understand practices, challenges, and opportunities related to the use of big data in statistical production in the region.

The interview will be recorded to ensure accurate reporting of your responses. The transcript of this interview will be shared with you for validation and to correct any inaccuracies.

Our goal here is to deepen, update, and complement the responses to the 2024 consultation.

DEVELOPMENT

We will discuss and ask questions about six different areas during the interview.

Before we begin, I will read to you what these areas are. They were outlined in the email we sent to arrange the interview.

The first questions are about four foundational areas related to the consultations:

1. Use of big data for official statistics
2. Use of big data for experimental statistics
3. Studies on the use of big data
4. Future plans for the use of big data

We will also discuss two topics related to the use of big data:

- A. Use of big data for other purposes
- B. Resources needed for the use of big data in your institute/office and resources available for sharing with other national institutes/offices

Before we start the questions on each area, we will announce/emphasize that we are beginning a new section and explain the purpose of the questions.

1. Use of Big Data for Official Statistics

We will start with the first question, which is related to the use of big data for official statistics. According to the UN Statistics Division, “official statistics are produced by government agencies and can inform debate and decision-making both by governments and the wider community” (United Nations Fundamental Principles of Official Statistics (UN FPOS)).

Q1. Your statistical institute/office reported that it already uses big data in the production of official statistics. We would like to know more details about this usage, such as how long it has been used, what type of big data, and what statistics you are producing based on this data. Could you share this information with us?

Q1. Your statistical institute/office reported that it does not use big data in the production of official statistics. We would like to know if there has been any change in this situation.

FOR THE INTERVIEWER:

For each example of official statistics produced with big data:

- Types of big data used
- Topics or themes addressed
- How long this approach has been used
- The process of collecting or obtaining this data
- Documentation available for this statistic

2. Use of Big Data for Experimental Statistics

Let's move on to the second question. The topic now is experimental statistics: whether they have been produced, what experiences you have, and other characteristics of this work. Experimental statistics are those developed to test new methods and data sources before being officially adopted.

Q2. Your statistical institute/office reported that it already uses big data in the production of experimental statistics. We would like to know more details about the use of experimental statistics, what type of big data is being used, which statistics you are producing based on this data, and whether you intend to use them as official statistics. Could you share this information with us?

Q2. Your statistical institute/office reported that it does not use big data in the production of experimental statistics. We would like to know if there has been any change in this situation.

FOR THE INTERVIEWER

For each example of experimental statistics produced with big data:

- Types of big data used
- Topics or themes addressed
- How long this approach has been used
- The process of collecting this data
- Other intended purposes for the same type of big data
- Predictions for whether experimental statistics will be used as official statistics; if not, why not
- Documentation available for the examples cited

3. Studies on the Use of Big Data

Q3. Changing the focus a bit, your statistical institute/office reported that it studies the use of big data for statistical production. We would like to know more details about these studies, such as what type of big data is being used and for which statistics. Could you tell us more about this?

Q3. Your statistical institute/office reported that it does not study the use of big data for statistical production. We would like to know if there has been any change in this situation.

FOR THE INTERVIEWER

- Projects dedicated to big data
- Main objectives of these studies
- Partnerships with universities or other institutions in this field
- Recent findings or discoveries that they could share with us

4. Future Plans for the Use of Big Data

Q4. Now, we would like to talk about the future. Your statistical institute/office reported that it has plans to expand or initiate new uses of big data for statistical production. Are there any fields or thematic areas in which you are investing to apply the use of big data?

Q4. Your statistical institute/office reported that it does not have plans to expand or initiate new uses of big data in statistical production. We would like to know if there has been any change in this situation.

FOR THE INTERVIEWER

- What type of big data would be used?
- Which areas are most promising for new applications of big data?
- Are there challenges to implementing these new applications?
- How do you see the impact of big data on the future of official and experimental statistics in your country?

5. Use of Big Data for Other Purposes

So far, we have discussed big data as an input or source of information for the direct production of statistics.

Now, we would like to know about experiences where big data is used as support or input for other activities.

For example, mobile phone data might be used to create a registry for sample selection in a survey. In this case, the mobile phone data itself is not used for to produce statistics, but as an input for planning another survey.

Q5. Does your statistical institute/office use big data for purposes other than the direct production of statistics?

FOR THE INTERVIEWER

- What are these purposes?
- How long has this been happening?
- Is this done in partnership with any other organization?

6. Necessary and Available Resources for the Use of Big Data in Institutes/Offices

Considering the situation of your institute/office, please share a bit about the resources necessary for the production of statistics using big data and the institutional expertise available to support the use of big data in statistical production, based on your experience with this type of data.

Q6.1. What resources do you think would be necessary for producing statistics using big data?

Q6.2. Does your Statistical Institute have any expertise in the use of big data that could be shared with other countries? If so, what expertise?

CLOSING

Thank you very much for sharing all this information and your experiences!

This was a very enriching conversation. Before we conclude, is there anything else you would like to add or any point you think is important to highlight?

With this, we conclude our interview. I would like to reaffirm that there will be a nominal list including the names of those who contributed to this work. Can we include your name, or would you prefer not to be listed?

Before we begin working with this information, we will share this transcript with you for validation and to correct any inaccuracies.

Once again, thank you very much for your participation!

Appendix C – Synthesis of the in-depth interviews

Argentina

Internacional Consultation on the use of Big Data in Latin America and the Caribbean

Date/Time: 24/07 - 13h.

Institution: Instituto Nacional de Estadística y Censos (INDEC).

Interviewe: Lic. Mariano Poledo - Director Nacional de Planificación y Relaciones Institucionales e Internacionales.

1. Use of Big Data for Official Statistics

Does not use big data for the production of official statistics.

2. Use of Big Data for Experimental Statistics

Does not use big data for the production of experimental statistics.

3. Studies on the Use of Big Data

Does not conduct studies on the use of big data.

4. Future Plans for the Use of Big Data

Scanner data: To be used for the Consumer Price Index (CPI).

Mobile phone data: To conduct mobility studies.

5. Use of Big Data for Other Purposes

Data from location of economics/ businesses: Provided by the Federal Administration of Public Revenue (AFIP), used for validation and sample construction for surveys.

Satellite imagery: Used to update administrative records of households for surveys.

6. Resources Needed for Producing Statistics with Big Data

Training: Requires skilled human resources at the forefront of data handling and the use of tools. Access to international best practices in the use of software and visualization tools.

Staff retention: Incentives to retain personnel and reduce migration to the private sector.

Legislation: Need for an updated regulatory framework to ensure access to data from private companies/ enterprises.

7. Expertise in Big Data Use to Share with Other Countries

Expertise in the production of foreign trade statistics using data provided by AFIP.

8. Additional Points Worth Highlighting

Utilizes administrative records, such as the Argentine Integrated Provisional System (SIPA - AFIP), for the production of statistics, including the wage index and national accounts. During the pandemic, data from a national pricing program were used, although this is no longer in use.

Working on the development of population and economic unit registers based on administrative data.

Maintains a web publication that could serve as a case study to share with regional countries on access to administrative data and statistics production.

Can share its experience in producing foreign trade statistics with data provided by AFIP.

Bonaire

Internacional Consultation on the use of Big Data in Latin America and the Caribbean

Date/Time: 11/09 – 9h

Institution: Statistics Netherlands Bonaire (CBS)

Interviewe: Barteld Braaksma, innovation manager, the Hague, The Netherlands

Henk van de Velden, advisor, Bonaire, Caribbean Netherlands

1. Use of Big Data for Official Statistics

Does not use big data for the production of official statistics.

2. Use of Big Data for Experimental Statistics

Does not use big data for the production of experimental statistics.

3. Studies on the Use of Big Data

Tourism information from websites such as hotel booking platforms and Airbnb was explored but saw little progress due to difficulties accessing relevant data.

During the COVID-19 pandemic, mobile phone data was used to study mobility and tourism, but legal and operational challenges hindered further development.

4. Future Plans for the Use of Big Data

A key future interest is using telecommunications data to measure population at specific times of the day. This would be especially useful for monitoring tourist pressure on coral reefs and assessing environmental impacts in Bonaire. However, these plans face legal and data access challenges.

5. Use of Big Data for Other Purposes

The institution did not mention specific uses of big data for purposes beyond statistics production in Bonaire.

6. Resources Needed for Producing Statistics with Big Data

Advanced technical expertise and data processing capabilities are based in the Netherlands, while Bonaire focuses on local data collection.

7. Expertise in Big Data Use to Share with Other Countries

Statistics Netherlands has extensive experience in the use of big data in Europe, including initiatives such as the Big Data Statistics Center.

8. Additional Points Worth Highlighting

It was suggested that establishing regional contacts with major data providers, such as telecommunications and aviation associations, could benefit Caribbean countries. Specifically, aviation traffic data provided by entities like IATA could be valuable.

Brazil

Internacional Consultation on the use of Big Data in Latin America and the Caribbean

Date/Time: 09/07 - 17h.

Institution: Instituto Brasileiro de Geografia e Estatística (IBGE).

Interviewee: Vladimir Gonçalves Miranda - Gerente da Gerência de Planejamento Conceitual da Coordenação de Índices de Preços.

1. Use of Big Data for Official Statistics

Utilizes web scraping techniques to collect price data for certain sectors, such as airfare and ride-hailing services. Data collection began between 2017 and 2018, and these methods were implemented in 2020.

2. Use of Big Data for Experimental Statistics

Information derived from data provided by the Special Secretariat of the Federal Revenue has been used to produce experimental indicators, published on the IBGE website.

Conducted a study on using social media data to monitor public perception/opinion about IBGE.

Uses open fiscal invoices as a basis for calculating "experimental" price indices, for example, for fuel (gasoline).

3. Studies on the Use of Big Data

Web scraping for collecting prices and other variables in sectors like automotive sales and rentals, lodging, pharmaceuticals, and electronic equipment.

Studies using fiscal invoice data, exploring its potential for family budget surveys.

Satellite imagery in agriculture and logistics, for evaluating cultivated areas and optimizing routes in the agricultural sector.

4. Future Plans for the Use of Big Data

Development of price indices and family budget statistics from fiscal invoice records.

Creation of the National System of Geography, Statistics, and Data, which could enhance access to administrative records and other big data sources.

5. Use of Big Data for Other Purposes

Extraction of product characteristics for electronics using detailed product information obtained through web scraping.

6. Resources Needed for Producing Statistics with Big Data

Data: Faster and broader access to big data sources and institutional empowerment to obtain big data.

Infrastructure: Strengthening and investing in IT infrastructure to store, process, and analyze large data volumes.

Strategic planning: Long-term planning for building and enhancing infrastructure.

Personnel: Investment in training and hiring qualified staff, such as data engineers, data scientists, and data analysts.

7. Expertise in Big Data Use to Share with Other Countries

Courses and webinars on using web scraping and scanner data for creating price indices through alternative data sources.

Natural language processing techniques for classifying economic activities.

Privacy-preserving techniques for sharing census data.

8. Additional Points Worth Highlighting

No additional issues were indicated.

Chile

Internacional Consultation on the use of Big Data in Latin America and the Caribbean

Date/Time: 10/07 - 17h.

Institution: Instituto Nacional de Estadísticas (INE).

Interviewee: Ignacio Agloni - Jefe Unidad de Gobierno de Datos (que contiene al equipo de Ciencia de Datos de la institución).

Klaus Lehmann – Jefe de Ciencia de Datos - Unidad de Gobierno de Datos.

1. Use of Big Data for Official Statistics

Does not use big data for the production of official statistics.

2. Use of Big Data for Experimental Statistics

Scanner data from point-of-sale systems for price analysis.

Water consumption data to predict household occupancy.

3. Studies on the Use of Big Data

Satellite imagery (Sentinel) for wildfire prevention, in collaboration with Inegi (Mexico).

4. Future Plans for the Use of Big Data

No future plans for the use of big data.

5. Use of Big Data for Other Purposes

Satellite imagery to create land-use maps for generating sampling frames for agricultural surveys.

Mobile device metadata to monitor the quality and integrity of field survey operations, aiming to enhance the quality of collected data and prevent fraud.

Satellite imagery for socioeconomic stratification of household survey samples, predicting the socioeconomic strata of primary sampling units. These studies are experimental and have not yet resulted in official publications.

6. Resources Needed for Producing Statistics with Big Data

Infrastructure: CPUs for processing satellite images and machine learning models, storage space for large data volumes, and sufficient memory for loading large-scale models.

Legislation: Solutions to legal restrictions on the use of data storage and processing platforms, limiting the use of cloud services.

Cloud Processing: Google Cloud is currently the most viable alternative, supported by available funds for cloud storage and data processing services.

Training: Expansion of employee training in new technologies and data science methods.

Personnel: Recruitment of new professional profiles such as data engineers, machine learning specialists, and cloud services architecture and scaling experts.

7. Expertise in Big Data Use to Share with Other Countries

Public repositories on GitHub and GitLab are made available, allowing other institutions to access and replicate developed solutions, such as those related to using satellite imagery for wildfire prevention.

8. Additional Points Worth Highlighting

Participation in a bilateral project with Inegi (Mexico) titled "Development of an open-source technological platform aimed at integrating different information sources to enhance the utilization of statistical institutes' products". This project, funded by international development cooperation agencies, aims to develop a Data Lake platform based on open-source tools.

Colombia

Internacional Consultation on the use of Big Data in Latin America and the Caribbean

Data/hora: 17/07 - 16h.

Institution: Departamento Administrativo Nacional de Estadística (DANE).

Interviewe: Victor Andres Arevalo Cabra – Coordinador GIT Indicadores de los ODS y seguimiento a la Agenda 2030.

1. Use of Big Data for Official Statistics

Does not use big data for the production of official statistics.

2. Use of Big Data for Experimental Statistics

Web scraping for estimating economic activity indicators.

Use of satellite imagery to calculate SDG indicators:

- 9.1.1: Population living in the street.
- 11.1.1: Inadequate housing.
- 11.2.1: Access to public transport.
- 11.3.1: Ratio of land consumption rate to population growth rate.
- 11.7.1: Access to open spaces.

3. Studies on the Use of Big Data

Satellite imagery combined with administrative records to measure school accessibility and estimate the multidimensional poverty index.

4. Future Plans for the Use of Big Data

Web scraping daily news to produce economic activity estimators, correlating with GDP.

Satellite imagery for new SDG indicators:

- 7.1.1: Access to electricity.
- 15.1.1: Vegetation coverage indicator.

Text mining over municipal development plans to identify policies associated with population dynamics, fiscal management, and sustainable territorial planning.

5. Use of Big Data for Other Purposes

Big data is used as support in constructing the geostatistical framework, integrating data from multiple sources to plan statistical operations and support activities like the National Population and Housing Census.

6. Resources Needed for Producing Statistics with Big Data

Infrastructure: Increased technological capacity, such as cloud servers, to process and store large data volumes.

Training: Need for specialist training in big data. Strategies to address challenges related to high turnover rates of these professionals, who are in high demand in the market.

7. Expertise in Big Data Use to Share with Other Countries

The institute has shared its expertise in regional workshops, particularly in estimating SDG indicators using satellite imagery.

Experience in natural language processing that could be valuable for other countries.

8. Additional Points Worth Highlighting

Use of massive administrative records, combining data from different sources to complement information in official statistics like National Accounts and the Population Census.

Ecuador

Internacional Consultation on the use of Big Data in Latin America and the Caribbean

Date/Time: 14/08 - 15h (17h no Brasil)

Institution: Instituto Nacional de Estadística y Censos (INEC)

Interviewee: Angel Chiluisa - Analista del Sistema de Registros Administrativos

1. Use of Big Data for Official Statistics

Does not use big data for official statistics.

2. Use of Big Data for Experimental Statistics

Analyzes tweets (from X, former Twitter) to generate sentiment indicators.

3. Studies on the Use of Big Data

Does not conduct studies on the use of big data.

4. Future Plans for the Use of Big Data

Plans to use big data in sectors such as social security, education, and economic statistics.

Web scraping for price collection.

Use of electricity consumption data as a proxy for property occupancy.

5. Use of Big Data for Other Purposes

Big data is used to assess the quality of administrative data, such as correcting errors in identifying individuals during field statistical operations, like resolving name and surname mismatches.

6. Resources Needed for Producing Statistics with Big Data

Robust technological infrastructure to store and process large volumes of data.

Personnel stability to manage big data technologies.

Continuous staff training.

Tools for access control and maintaining data confidentiality.

7. Expertise in Big Data Use to Share with Other Countries

Development of standardized national population registers.

Techniques for massive data processing using Apache Hadoop with computer clusters.

8. Additional Points Worth Highlighting

Importance of establishing a cooperation network among statistical institutions and the potential to expand their data laboratories for an international audience.

Guatemala

Internacional Consultation on the use of Big Data in Latin America and the Caribbean

Date/Time: 26/07 - 10h.

Institution: Instituto Nacional de Estadística (INE).

Interviewee: Roberto Antonio De León García – Director de Informática.

1. Use of Big Data for Official Statistics

Does not use big data for the production of official statistics.

2. Use of Big Data for Experimental Statistics

Web scraping to generate a consumer price index.

3. Studies on the Use of Big Data

Does not conduct studies on the use of big data.

4. Future Plans for the Use of Big Data

Urban mobility, despite challenges with the coverage and reliability of public transportation card data.

5. Use of Big Data for Other Purposes

Satellite imagery for preparing survey samples and cartography to plan statistical operations.

6. Resources Needed for Producing Statistics with Big Data

Infrastructure: Improvement of technological infrastructure, both locally and in the cloud, including enhanced processing and storage capacity for servers and connectivity to enable efficient data exchange with other institutions.

Basic Infrastructure: Overcoming bottlenecks in stable access to electricity and the internet in remote areas to enable the use of big data on a national scale.

7. Expertise in Big Data Use to Share with Other Countries

Does not have expertise to share.

8. Additional Points Worth Highlighting

While there are no current studies on the use of big data, plans exist to integrate data from various public institutions through dedicated APIs to facilitate information exchange.

Developing infrastructure to interconnect with other public institutions, such as the National Civil Registry (RENAP). This includes expanding technological infrastructure and digitizing processes that are currently manual.

Mexico

Internacional Consultation on the use of Big Data in Latin America and the Caribbean

Date/Time: 11/07 - 10h.

Institution: Instituto Nacional de Estadística y Geografía (INEGI).

Interviewee: Elio Atenógenes Villaseñor García - Director del Laboratorio de Ciencia de Datos y Métodos Modernos de Información, Dirección General Adjunta de Investigación, Dirección General de Integración, Análisis e Investigación, Instituto Nacional de Estadística y Geografía.

1. Use of Big Data for Official Statistics

Does not use big data for the production of official statistics.

2. Use of Big Data for Experimental Statistics

Social media data processing (Twitter) for sentiment analysis and generating a daily positivity index. This was discontinued due to changes in X's (former Twitter) data access policies.

Nowcasting models integrating multiple sources, including Google Trends data and Twitter user mobility, to create the Timely Economic Activity Index (IOAE).

Satellite imagery to create vegetation and surface water indices, used for monitoring vegetation and water bodies.

3. Studies on the Use of Big Data

Language models based on Spanish Wikipedia data to categorize open-ended survey responses.

Satellite imagery to estimate agricultural production.

Satellite imagery for analyzing urban area growth.

Satellite imagery for assessing road pavement conditions.

Banking data (in partnership with private institutions) to evaluate consumption and income.

Natural language processing of news articles to measure violence intensity and forced displacement.

4. Future Plans for the Use of Big Data

Mobile phone data for research projects.

Navigation data for projects related to trade.

Web scraping to obtain and update information on economic units, complementing the national register.

5. Use of Big Data for Other Purposes

Web scraping to identify economic activities, contributing to the digital economy.

Satellite imagery with artificial intelligence to identify and map sports fields (soccer).

6. Resources Needed for Producing Statistics with Big Data

Infrastructure: High computational capacity is required to develop language models and process large data volumes.

Access to data: Challenges in obtaining continuous and stable access to data from sources such as mobile phone and maritime navigation.

Partnerships: Collaboration with universities and research centers for algorithm development.

7. Expertise in Big Data Use to Share with Other Countries

Algorithms for coding open-ended responses using language models.

Integration of big data sources with statistical models to create timely economic indicators (nowcasting).

Methodologies for geospatial analysis and creating vegetation and surface water indices using satellite imagery.

Web scraping for data collection and analysis of economic activity units.

8. Additional Points Worth Highlighting

No additional points were raised.

Paraguay

Internacional Consultation on the use of Big Data in Latin America and the Caribbean

Date/Time: 13/08 - 12h

Institution: Instituto Nacional de Estadística-Paraguay

Interviewee: Maria Teresa Chica

Cargo: Directora de Tecnología de la Información y Conectividad Informática

1. Use of Big Data for Official Statistics

Does not use big data for official statistics.

2. Use of Big Data for Experimental Statistics

Experiments with urban mobility surveys, such as using transportation cards and users' fingerprints and addresses to measure distances to transportation points.

3. Studies on the Use of Big Data

No studies are conducted on the use of big data.

4. Future Plans for the Use of Big Data

Use of big data to indicate housing occupancy.

Data from Twitter (X) and Facebook for citizen perception analysis and communication strategy development.

Telephony data to identify temporary housing.

5. Use of Big Data for Other Purposes

Use of big data to extract samples from databases such as censuses and household surveys.

Use of artificial intelligence and machine learning to code open-ended variables from the National Population and Housing Census, such as geographic location, occupation, and migration, to produce socioeconomic and demographic statistics.

Satellite imagery is acquired to support updated cartography for the country, purchased from the Maxar satellite.

6. Resources Needed for Producing Statistics with Big Data

Enhanced data security, especially for cloud storage.

Investments in IT infrastructure and paid licenses for advanced data visualization and analysis tools.

Increased processing capacity and continuous data updates from partner institutions.

Access to more databases produced by other institutions.

7. Expertise in Big Data Use to Share with Other Countries

No experiences to share.

8. Additional Points Worth Highlighting

Suggested the creation of a regional working group among Latin American and Caribbean countries to share experiences and best practices in using big data.

Continuous collaboration among technical teams from different countries to collectively advance the use of big data for statistics.

Peru

Internacional Consultation on the use of Big Data in Latin America and the Caribbean

Date/Time: 31/07 - 10h.

Institution: Instituto Nacional de Estadística e Informática (INEI).

Interviewe: Manuel Matos Alvarado, Director Técnico de la Oficina Técnica de Informática.
José Llanos Solórzano, Especialista en Integración de Base de Datos de la Dirección Nacional de Censos y Encuestas.

Silvia Angulo Vera, Cartógrafo II de la Dirección Nacional de Censos y Encuestas.

David Ramirez Barrera, Especialista Cartográfico de la Dirección Nacional de Censos y Encuestas.

Yonamder Tomaylla Yupanqui, Especialista de Información Cartográfica Espacial de la Dirección Nacional de Censos y Encuestas.

Rosa María Boza Castro, Directora Ejecutiva de Cooperación Técnica de la Oficina Técnica de Planificación Presupuesto y Cooperación Técnica.

1. Use of Big Data for Official Statistics

Does not use big data for the production of official statistics.

2. Use of Big Data for Experimental Statistics

Satellite imagery (from Google Maps servers and the national satellite CONIDA) is used for cartography, identifying urban and rural growth areas, and measuring building heights through shadow analysis on satellite images.

3. Studies on the Use of Big Data

Does not conduct consistent studies on the use of big data.

4. Future Plans for the Use of Big Data

Implementation of a Data Lake to integrate data from various areas, such as censuses, cartography, and economic indicators.

Application of Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), including the use of urban data to classify cities' levels of urbanization.

Use of big data from private sources, such as information from large supermarket chains, to improve price data collection.

5. Use of Big Data for Other Purposes

Does not use big data for other purposes.

6. Resources Needed for Producing Statistics with Big Data

Modernization of the data center.

Cloud-based data processing.

Continuous training and capacity building for human resources, especially in big data technologies and cloud data administration.

7. Expertise in Big Data Use to Share with Other Countries

Does not have consolidated experience in big data to share with other countries.

8. Additional Points Worth Highlighting

Primarily uses big data for producing official statistics related to poverty mapping, with databases derived from censuses, surveys, and administrative records.

Dominican Republic

Internacional Consultation on the use of Big Data in Latin America and the Caribbean

Date/Time: 16/07 - 15h.

Institution: Oficina Nacional de Estadística (ONE).

Interviewee: Miosotis Rivas Peña - Directora General.

Paola Rodríguez - Encargada de Estadísticas Ambientales - Dirección de Estadísticas Demográficas, Sociales y Ambientales.

Leidy Ventura - Coordinadora de Estadísticas Ambientales - Dirección de Estadísticas Demográficas, Sociales y Ambientales.

Yuleika Beriguete - Analista de Estadísticas Coyunturales y de Precios - Dirección de Estadísticas Económicas.

1. Use of Big Data for Official Statistics

Does not use big data for the production of official statistics.

2. Use of Big Data for Experimental Statistics

Free satellite imagery and drone-captured images are used to calculate areas affected by the sargassum phenomenon in the country's coastal zones.

Google Maps imagery is used to calculate green areas in the Santo Domingo region.

3. Studies on the Use of Big Data

Web scraping to collect prices for airline tickets and hotel reservations. (Big data exploration project discontinued due to technical limitations.)

Mobile phone company data is used to model human mobility in response to natural disasters. (Study in progress.)

4. Future Plans for the Use of Big Data

Development of an Environmental Statistics Atlas using big data, including satellite imagery, to map environmental variables such as climate, deforestation, and population density.

5. Use of Big Data for Other Purposes

No examples of use for purposes other than direct statistical production.

6. Resources Needed for Producing Statistics with Big Data

Legislation: Updating the regulatory framework to allow greater access to financial resources and institutional support.

Resources: Securing financial resources to acquire satellite data with complete attributes and drones equipped with specialized software.

Personnel: Increasing the number of trained human resources.

Capacity Building: Permanent strengthening of technical capabilities.

7. Expertise in Big Data Use to Share with Other Countries

Experience measuring the sargassum phenomenon has already been shared with institutions such as Inegi (Mexico).

8. Additional Points Worth Highlighting

Collaboration with OpenStreetMap and the NGO Humanitarian OpenStreetMap Team (HOT) to enhance capabilities in using drones for data collection.

Uruguay

Internacional Consultation on the use of Big Data in Latin America and the Caribbean

Date/Time: 10/07 - 11h.

Institution: Instituto Nacional de Estadística (INE).

Interviewee: Federico Segui - Vice Director General.

1. Use of Big Data for Official Statistics

Does not use big data for the production of official statistics.

2. Use of Big Data for Experimental Statistics

Satellite images from Google (Open Buildings) for building registration, including built surface area and the number of floors.

Mobility data from mobile phones during the pandemic. Access to these data was lost post-pandemic, and negotiations with companies and regulatory entities are ongoing.

3. Studies on the Use of Big Data

Web scraping using APIs from e-commerce platforms (such as Mercado Livre) to create a price index.

4. Future Plans for the Use of Big Data

No future plans for the use of big data were declared.

5. Use of Big Data for Other Purposes

Electricity consumption data is used to verify and confirm survey data and to plan the census by estimating household occupancy. These data are provided by the national electricity company.

6. Resources Needed for Producing Statistics with Big Data

Personnel: Shortage of qualified human resources, such as data scientists, and difficulty retaining these professionals due to competition with the private sector.

Infrastructure: Challenges in processing large volumes of data.

Partnerships: Seeking collaborations with universities and international organizations to overcome personnel and infrastructure limitations.

7. Expertise in Big Data Use to Share with Other Countries

Experience in public-private collaboration for the use of mobile phone mobility data. This project has been documented and shared in various international forums and webinars.

8. Additional Points Worth Highlighting

Use of administrative records for producing official statistics, such as labor market indicators, based on payment operations with social security. This experience has been shared with the national statistical agency of Tunisia.

Conducted a pilot census based on administrative records, comparing it with the traditional census, yielding very similar results.

Calculation of the Consumer Price Index (CPI) using data from large supermarket chains through product price lists.

Appendix D – List of people interviewed

List of people interviewed with position, by Country

People interviewed and position	COUNTRY
Mariano Poledo - Director Nacional de Planificación y Relaciones Institucionales e Internacionales.	Argentina
Vladimir Gonçalves Miranda - Gerente da Gerência de Planejamento Conceitual da Coordenação de Índices de Preços.	Brazil
Barteld Braaksma, innovation manager, the Hague, The Netherlands Henk van de Velden, advisor, Bonaire, Caribbean Netherlands	Bonaire
Ignacio Agloni - Jefe Unidad de Gobierno de Datos (que contiene al equipo de Ciencia de Datos de la institución). Klaus Lehmann - Coordinador Técnico equipo de Ciencia de Datos - Unidad de Gobierno de Datos.	Chile
Victor Andres Arevalo Cabra – Coodinador GIT Indicadores de los ODS y seguimiento a la Agenda 2030	Colombia
Angel Chiluisa - Analista del Sistema de Registros Administrativos	Ecuador
Roberto Antonio De León García - Director de Informática	Guatemala
Elio Atenógenes Villaseñor García - Director del Laboratorio de Ciencia de Datos y Métodos Modernos de Información, Dirección General Adjunta de Investigación, Dirección General de Integración, Análisis e Investigación, Instituto Nacional de Estadística y Geografía.	Mexico
María Teresa Chica - Directora de Tecnología de la Información y Conectividad Informática - Instituto Nacional de Estadística-Paraguay	Paraguay
Manuel Matos Alvarado, Director Técnico de la Oficina Técnica de Informática. José Llanos Solórzano, Especialista en Integración de Base de Datos de la Dirección Nacional de Censos y Encuestas. Silvia Angulo Vera, Cartógrafo II de la Dirección Nacional de Censos y Encuestas. David Ramirez Barrera, Especialista Cartográfico de la Dirección Nacional de Censos y Encuestas. Yonamder Tomaylla Yupanqui, Especialista de Información Cartográfica Espacial de la Dirección Nacional de Censos y Encuestas. Rosa María Boza Castro, Directora Ejecutiva de Cooperación Técnica de la Oficina Técnica de Planificación Presupuesto y Cooperación Técnica.	Peru
Paola Rodríguez - Encargada de Estadísticas Ambientales - Dirección de Estadísticas Demográficas, Sociales y Ambientales. Leidy Ventura - Coordinadora de Estadísticas Ambientales - Dirección de Estadísticas Demográficas, Sociales y Ambientales. Yuleika Beriguete - Analista de Estadísticas Coyunturales y de Precios - Dirección de Estadísticas Económicas.	Dominican Republic
Federico Segui - Vice Director General.	Uruguay

Appendix E – Videos on the subject of big data by date

Videos about big data by data, content and language

Date	Content / Title	Language
06/12/2021	VGI Initiatives in Latin America	English
21/02/2022	I Workshop on Big Data for Official Statistics: Introducción al web scraping aplicado a índices de precios	English, Spanish and Portuguese
23/02/2022		
25/02/2022		
05/07/2022	Conference: Using Big Data and Machine Learning for Land Cover and Land Use Mapping: Challenges to Mapping Accuracy	English, Spanish and Portuguese
06/07/2022		
07/07/2022		
21/09/2022	Webinário: Ferramentas de Capacitação da UN Big Data	Portuguese
08/11/2022	Opening ceremony of the 2022 UN Big Data Hackathon Brazil Satellite Location	Portuguese
17/11/2022	Webinar: Big Data for Official Statistics	Spanish
15/12/2022	Webinar: Using Mobile Phone Data for Official Statistics on Migration	English, Spanish and Portuguese
09/02/2023	Webinar: Using Mobile Phone Data for Official Statistics on Tourism	English
09/03/2023	Webinar: Using Mobile Phone Data for Official Statistics on Population	English, and Spanish
06/04/2023	Webinar: Using Mobile Phone Data on Displacement and Disaster Statistics	English
04/05/2023	Webinar: Using Mobile Phone Data for Official Statistics on Information Society	English, and Spanish
01/06/2023	Webinar: Using Mobile Phone Data for Official Statistics on Transportation and Commuting	English
06/07/2023	Webinar: Mobile Phone Data Access for Official Statistics	English
31/07/2023	III Workshop on Big Data for Official Statistics: Using satellite images for the calculus of the 11.7.1 SDG Indicator	Spanish
02/08/2023		
04/08/2023		
03/08/2023	Webinar: Using Mobile Phone Data on Trending Topics	English
09/08/2023	Webinar series Road to Punta del Este Data Festival: Use of Earth Observation for Official Statistics	English, and Spanish
06/09/2023	Webinar series Road to Punta del Este Data Festival: Web Scraping for Prices	English, and Spanish
11/10/2023	Webinar series Road to Punta del Este Data Festival: Data Science in Official Statistics	English, and Spanish
15/03/2024	Webinar: Weighting a Non-Probabilistic Sample to Estimate Internet Quality Indicators for Brazilian Schools	English, Spanish and Portuguese
19/04/2024	Webinar: Correction of bias in estimating COVID-19 cases in Brazil	English, Spanish and Portuguese

Date	Content / Title	Language
17/05/2024	Webinar: Sampling and price inference for virtual markets	English, Spanish and Portuguese
18/06/2024	Webinar: Use of mobile phone data for public policies	English
24/06/2024	V Workshop on the Use of Big Data for Official Statistics: “ARIES (Artificial Intelligence for Environment and Sustainability) for Mitigation and Adaptation Indicators in the face of Climate Change”.	Spanish
26/06/2024		
28/06/2024		
31/07/2024	Webinar: UN Task Team on Training, Skills and Capacity Development	Spanish
25/09/2024	Webinar: Climate Change and Disaster Metrics in Latin America and the Caribbean: Advances and Challenges	Spanish
16/10/2024	Webinar: Climate Change Indicators: Harnessing the Potential of New Data Sources for better measurement of Tourism Sustainability	English

Source: United Nations Regional Hub for Big Data in Brazil, <https://hub.ibge.gov.br/videos.htm>. Access in October 2024.